

THE ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS ABOUT THE STATE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN SLOVAKIA

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Introduction

The present document is based on the Analysis of Findings about the State of the Education System in Slovakia delivered by the [Learning Makes Sense Initiative](#) aiming at preparing the comprehensive reform of the whole education system. The analysis covered five areas: customised support for all learners; training and development of teachers and professional staff; education content and methods; education openness and permeability; and governance and financing in education. It aimed to identify the major problems in the education system, together with their causes and relationships. The analysis is based on an extensive qualitative and quantitative data collection carried out in 2017–2019. The analytical framework was the education vision formulated in 2016, based on discussions with numerous Slovak and international experts. The aim of the data collection was to find out what prevents us from achieving the envisaged state as defined in the education vision. Problems related to education policy as well as its implementation in various contexts were examined. In total, 656 respondents representing all the important actors in the education system took part in the in 421 individual and group interviews. The quantitative survey aimed to verify the scope of the problems identified, and in total 15,322 respondents participated, from various positions in pre-primary up to higher education levels, as well as professionals in human resources (HR). In the Slovak context, this is unique in terms of the sample size and the complex approach.

As already mentioned the findings were analysed in these five areas: customised support for all learners; training and development of teachers and professional staff; education content and methods; education openness and permeability; and governance and financing in education. Each area contains findings for all education levels (from pre-primary to higher education). This document is a collection of the overview chapters summing up the key findings in the five analyzed areas, and the [key aspects of methodology used during the research](#). A separate chapter, available only in Slovak, covers the demographic basis as related to education reform proposals, describing the expected major trends in the student and pupils population up to 2030. The Learning Makes Sense Initiative contracted the Central European Labour Studies Institute to prepare a study on employers' experience with employing graduates with high/middle/low qualifications on the Slovak labour market. The key findings of this study are available in a [separate document](#).

Despite the analysis being extensive, its ambition was not to cover all the problems of the Slovak education system. The aim was to present the research findings and encourage expert discussion on the problems, their causes and context, and especially their possible solutions. Findings from the analysis formed the basis of the reform proposals presented by the Learning Makes Sense initiative in February 2020.

The full text of the analysis in Slovak is available here: analyza.todarozum.sk

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Customised support for learners

In addition to acquiring knowledge and skills, education should also prepare people for life in a diverse society. Therefore, it should reduce inequalities, address the needs and develop the potential of all learners as much as possible, and prepare learners to succeed in their personal, civic and professional life. This objective can be fulfilled only if the schools can address the diverse learning needs children have and provide them with high-quality and customised support.

As in other countries, learners in Slovakia are entitled to receive support in education based on the concept of special educational needs (SEN). This concept was first introduced in the 1970s in the United Kingdom and aimed to divert attention from medically-based categories of disability towards their consequences for the learning process. In Slovakia, SEN status is granted to children with physical disabilities, talented children, and children from socially disadvantaged backgrounds.

The findings in the *Learning Makes Sense* project indicate that the current concept of SEN has several limitations. These limitations are related both to its legal definition and its implementation in practice. What gives rise to special needs is mostly ascribed to factors relating to the child themselves (child's disability or talent), or issues in the family background. Regrettably, such an approach diverts attention from existing barriers and responsibilities pertaining to schools and the education system. Moreover, as children are categorised based on their disabilities or talents, the individual differences in their educational needs are disregarded, yet the differences within a single "category" can be very significant. The very principle of categorising children seems to be undesirable, because each child has individual needs that the system should primarily address.

Another problem is an increasing proportion of SEN designated children and pupils. The proportion of SEN designated pupils at primary schools in Slovakia is the fourth highest in Europe and it has increased by more than a third over the past decade. At primary schools, almost one in five pupils are granted SEN status of some kind, while in certain districts this holds for a third or even a half of all pupils. Despite this fact, not all children that would need support and a customised approach to their education receive it in practice, because they are not covered by the current categories of SEN students. More than a half of teachers and professionals in education confirmed in the questionnaire survey that such children attended their school. These children can be, for example, those whose mother tongue differs from the language of instruction at their school, children in institutional care (orphanages), or children facing acute or long-term crises in their families.

Based on the *Learning Makes Sense* findings, the increasing proportion of SEN designated children can be related to a more precise diagnostic process, the demands placed on children, and the current system of school financing. Paradoxically, providing a higher financial contribution for pupils with physical disabilities or talents can indirectly support excessive diagnostics for those groups of children for whom schools receive inadequate or even no funds to carry out support measures. Such examples include children from socially excluded Roma localities where one in five children are diagnosed with a mental disability. However, there are several indications that the diagnosis of mild mental disability, i.e. serious and irreversible damage to cognitive abilities, is also granted to children failing in education due to other reasons, where late and inadequate support measures are a common feature. Since receiving support is conditional upon granting a diagnosis, preventive measures at schools are rather limited. Yet such prevention could reduce the likelihood that the child's risky development might lead to disadvantage or even defect.

Aside from the high number of SEN designated children, another problem is that only half of them attend mainstream classrooms with their peers. Yet findings from relevant international research sources show that such a practice has negative effects on learning outcomes and social skills, both for children with disabilities and other children. Slovakia occupies a discouraging first place among European states in its proportion of primary school pupils educated separately in special needs classrooms and special needs schools. The number of children in special needs education remained

almost stable during the past decade, pointing to a relative stability of capacity in special needs education. A particular problem is that there is “no passage” between the mainstream and special needs schools. Special needs schools and classrooms are not used to providing temporary support for a child, but rather constitute a permanently separated education path with most children being tracked into it as they start their schooling. The separation of both education paths is reflected in limited co-operation between mainstream and special needs schools. However, the Learning Makes Sense findings show that staff at both types of school would appreciate more co-operation.

The education system is unable to provide conditions for educating pupils with various needs in mainstream schools, and this has an extremely negative impact on certain groups of children. For some children with physical disabilities, this situation results in their total exclusion from education at schools and their forced homeschooling. Also, a large proportion of Roma children are educated in ethnically homogeneous Roma classrooms or schools. Currently, education policies cannot prevent the segregation of Roma children and some policies even indirectly support it. Separate education is the most commonly used form in the case of intellectually gifted pupils. International research findings show that this form of education is not optimal, neither for children with special needs, nor children without any disabilities or gifted children.

An important finding is that despite the prevailing trend for SEN designated children being educated separately, most survey respondents from the mainstream schools tend to agree that the majority of SEN designated groups should be educated in mainstream schools (in their special or regular classes). However, many mainstream schools do not have adequate conditions in terms of their organisation, funding, staff and space to educate these children. There is a lack of teaching assistants and moreover, their duties are sometimes not effectively delegated, leading to an increased demand for assistants in the system. Many schools lack professional staff (SEN teachers, school psychologists etc.) and medical and personal assistance services for children with physical disabilities remain virtually non-existent. Apart from the lack of staff, there are no precisely defined standards for their work, including a model for co-operation with teachers and their work at schools.

According to respondents from the *Learning Makes Sense* survey, another problem is that teachers in mainstream schools are not ready to educate children with diverse needs. At group interviews, students in teaching programmes pointed out the lack of attention placed on this issue in their pre-service training, and no remedy is provided during in-service teacher training. Almost three quarters of teachers at mainstream schools participating in the survey did not attend any further training on supporting children with diverse needs in education. Despite two thirds of teachers expressing a need to attend such training, it is not actually available. According to the international survey TALIS 2018, it is in this field that the highest proportion of current teachers feel they need to develop professionally.

At the same time, the Learning Makes Sense findings indicate that even at special needs schools, conditions for educating children with various needs are not optimal. Respondents from special needs schools claim there is a significant lack of funds and staff in this education segment (teaching assistants, professional staff, other support service staff). At the same time, many mainstream and special needs schools lack adequate support from advisory and prevention centres. Across Slovakia, respondents express widely varying experiences with the form and quality of support provided by advisory and prevention centres. While the centres are currently understaffed and underfunded, this situation can also be explained by the lack of quality standards for services provided by centres, and the inadequate methodological advice received by the centres themselves.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative data](#) in the Learning Makes Sense are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Diversity of children's learning needs

Children and pupils have diverse learning needs, but the system only fulfils the needs of some of them

Separate education of SEN designated children

In pre-primary to secondary schools, the prevailing trend is for separate education of children with diverse needs

Problems in education of SEN designated children

Many barriers prevent schools from being ready to educate children with diverse needs

Selected supporting measures in education

Conclusions

Education should be a quality public service enabling all people to lead a decent and meaningful life, regardless of their health or social conditions. This is only possible if schools do not exacerbate the initial disadvantages children might have, but instead, thanks to well established support at schools, children can experience success both there and later in their lives.

According to the Learning Makes Sense analysis findings, the Slovak education system is unable to sufficiently address the diversity of children's learning needs, and this negatively impacts on certain groups of children (children with physical disabilities or children from excluded Roma communities) that have been systematically excluded from access to quality education. A high proportion of children educated in separate schools and classes for students with the same/similar disabilities runs contrary to the international commitments and trends supporting education of all children in their local communities. It limits interaction of these children with the rest of society and increases their chances of exclusion from the labour market or society in the future.

Separate education also prevents children without a diagnosed disability or talent from learning to live in a diverse society and benefit from professional and customised support. Moreover, in a situation where almost a fifth of primary school pupils have been SEN designated, and a significant group of children are ineligible for additional support despite needing it, we should ask whether it wouldn't make more sense to change the education system as such, instead of investing in "special" support for SEN designated children. All children could thus develop to their maximum potential.

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Diversity of children's learning needs

Children and pupils have diverse learning needs, but the system fulfils the needs of only some of them

Similar to other countries, learners in Slovakia are entitled to receive support in education based on the special educational needs concept (SEN). The Learning Makes Sense findings indicate the limitations of this concept, arising both from its ideological background and its application in practice. A deficit-based SEN definition that ascribes cause to a child's disadvantages or disabilities, or to the family, diverts attention from the barriers children might face from schools and the education system. Due to this rather rigid categorisation of children by their disadvantages or disabilities, individual differences children have in their learning needs are disregarded. At the same time, children who do not match the current SEN categories are ineligible for support and a customised approach. Another problem is the increasing proportion of children and pupils designated as SEN. At primary schools, almost one in five pupils are granted SEN status of some kind, while in certain districts this holds for a third or even a half of all pupils. Based on the Learning Makes Sense findings, an increasing proportion of SEN designations can be related to a more precise diagnostic process, the demands placed on children, and the current system of school financing. Providing a higher financial contribution per pupil with SEN can indirectly support excessive diagnosing of children and thus contribute to an increasing number of SEN designated children. Since receiving support is conditional upon "diagnosis", preventive measures are rather limited. Also, it can contribute to a high proportion of certain groups (e.g. Roma children or children from orphanages) among children with a diagnosed physical disability. The fact that the mild mental disability diagnosis applies to almost one in five children living in excluded Roma communities might offer an example. Having a mild mental disability diagnosis de facto excludes these children from education, because most of them attend primary education separated from their peers and their further options to continue at secondary schools are limited. The current system results in a lack of personal and financial resources at advisory and prevention centres. Due to this, these centres' main focus is on establishing a diagnosis rather than providing the efficient support which is crucial for the child's further education.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the next sections:

Limitations of the SEN concept

The concept of special educational needs has several limitations

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Increase in the proportion of children who need support

Increase in the proportion of children/pupils who need support in education

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Unequal distribution of SEN designated children

Children and pupils who need support are distributed unequally at schools

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Issues related to the mild mental disability diagnosis

Establishing the diagnosis of mild mental disability excludes a group of pupils from mainstream education

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SEN related to establishing a diagnosis, not support

Identifying special educational needs is often related mostly to establishing a diagnosis, rather than facilitating efficient support

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Conclusions

Education should be a quality public service enabling all people to lead a decent and meaningful life, regardless of their health or social conditions. Such an objective can be fulfilled only if the school can address the diverse learning needs children have, and provide them with the quality and customised support that would enable them to experience success both there and also later in their lives. The way education policy defines who is eligible for educational support, and under what conditions, is vital for establishing this support. The Learning Makes Sense findings indicate that current definitions of special educational needs does entitle all children in need of support to be eligible for it, but to some extent it limits application of preventive measures. At the same time, it impacts on the efficiency of supporting measures, because instead of adapting the education process to children's needs, it rather results in negative labelling of children and their frequent exclusion from mainstream classes and schools. In a situation where almost a fifth of primary school pupils have been granted SEN status and a significant group of children are ineligible for additional support despite needing it (as they are not included in a particular category), we should ask whether it wouldn't make more sense to change the education system as such, so that all children could develop to their maximum potential, instead of investing in "special" support for SEN designated children.

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Separate education of SEN designated children

In pre-primary to secondary schools, the prevailing trend is for separate education of children with diverse needs

Slovakia ranks first among European countries and has the highest proportion of primary school pupils educated in special needs education streams. The highest proportion of children in special needs schools and classes is in Eastern Slovakia. The number of children in special needs education has remained almost stable over the past decade, pointing to a relative stability of capacity in special needs education. One of the barriers to the inclusion of children with special educational needs (SEN) in mainstream schools is also the conviction that the separate education of these children is appropriate, and this was confirmed by the Learning Makes Sense questionnaire survey. However, most respondents from mainstream schools tend to agree that children with various needs should be educated in mainstream schools (in their regular or special classes), also pointing out that adequate conditions must be provided. Particularly, the inadequate conditions for educating SEN designated children in mainstream schools are the reason why a portion of these children are diverted to special needs schools. Thus, the parental right to choose the most appropriate form of education for their child is de facto limited. Another problem is that there is no passage between the mainstream and special needs schools. Special needs schools and classrooms are not used to providing temporary support for a child, but rather constitute a permanently separated education path, with most children being tracked onto it as soon as they start their schooling. This separation of education paths is reflected in limited co-operation between mainstream and special needs schools, although the staff at both types of school would appreciate it, according to the Learning Makes Sense survey findings. The education system is unable to provide conditions for educating pupils with various needs, and this has an extremely negative impact on certain groups of children. For some children with physical disabilities, this situation results in their total exclusion from education at schools and their forced homeschooling. A large proportion of Roma children are educated in ethnically homogeneous Roma classrooms or schools. A huge problem is that they form a majority of pupils in special classes and schools for children with a mild mental disability, and this limits their opportunities to complete full primary and lower secondary education and continue at a secondary school. Currently, education policies cannot effectively prevent the segregation of Roma children and some policies even indirectly support it. Separated education is also the most commonly used form for intellectually gifted pupils. International research findings show that separated education is not optimal for children with special needs, nor children without any disabilities or gifted children.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the next sections:

Over-representation of children in special needs schools

Almost half the children with special educational needs are educated in a special needs education track

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Separate education of SEN designated children is considered to be more appropriate

Separate education of children with special educational needs is still considered to be more appropriate

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No passage between mainstream and special needs schools

The mainstream and special needs education tracks are separate and without a passage between them

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Exclusion of certain children with physical disabilities from education

A portion of children with physical disabilities are completely excluded from education

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Roma children segregation

A high proportion of Roma children are educated separately from their peers

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Separate education of children with talents

Selection of children by their intellectual abilities is taking place already at primary schools

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Conclusions

A long-term high proportion of children educated in separate schools and classes for students with the same/similar disabilities or talents runs contrary to the international commitments and trends supporting the education of all children in their local communities. It reflects a relative stability in terms of special needs schools' capacities and the barriers pertaining to addressing the natural diversity of children on the part of mainstream schools. Limiting interactions between various groups of children in education and the existence of separate education structures for children with diagnosed special needs or for children of other ethnicities can limit the extent and variety of their social networks, and increase the chances of their exclusion from the labour market or society in the future. Separate education also prevents children without a diagnosed disability or talent from learning to live in a diverse society. As SEN designated children are educated in specialised conditions by various professionals, then the pupils without a diagnosed disability or talent cannot fully benefit from this care and customised education. A system supporting early tracking in education based on children's abilities, or even their social background or ethnicity, further deepens the differences in their learning outcomes and contributes to strengthening social inequalities in society whilst at the same time loosening social cohesion.

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Problems in education of SEN designated children

Many barriers prevent schools from being ready to educate children with diverse needs

One of the reasons behind tracking a large proportion of learners with special educational needs (SEN) into special needs education tracks could be that school management and teachers in mainstream schools perceive themselves to be insufficiently prepared to educate these children. This was confirmed in the Learning Makes Sense survey regarding learners with physical disabilities, especially by respondents from kindergartens. Less than a quarter of them considered their own school ready to educate these children. The ability of schools to address the diversity of learners is influenced by many problems they face in the education process. They relate to insufficient organisation, finance, personnel and space. The biggest challenge according to respondents from mainstream schools is the diversity of children's needs as such, coupled with a high number of students per class, thereby inhibiting a customised approach from teachers. Although classroom size in Slovakia is similar relative to other EU or OECD countries, Slovakia has a higher average proportion of pupils per teacher at pre-primary and primary education levels. Moreover, there is often no teaching assistant to compensate for this state. Almost half of respondents from kindergartens and primary schools perceive the lack of teaching assistants to be a problem. Schools also lack other professional staff (school psychologists, SEN teachers, etc.). This is related to teachers receiving insufficient methodological support in educating SEN designated children, perceived as a problem by a fifth of respondents. This kind of support is important because teachers are not sufficiently prepared to teach children with diverse needs. Such support is needed both in pre-service and in-service teacher training. However, the Learning Makes Sense findings indicate that even at special needs schools, conditions for educating children with various needs are not optimal. Respondents from special needs schools claim there is a significant lack of funds and staff in this education segment (teaching assistants, professional staff, other support service staff). Also, Learning Makes Sense survey respondents claim that many schools lack sufficient support for educating SEN designated children from advisory and prevention centres. As many as a quarter of teachers at mainstream schools and a majority of teaching assistants responded in the survey that they do not get any external professional and methodological support at all. Across Slovakia, respondents expressed widely varying experiences with the form and quality of support provided by advisory and prevention centres. This could be caused by the lack of quality standards for services provided by centres, and inadequate methodological advice received by the centres themselves.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the following sections:

Preparedness of schools to address the diversity of children's needs

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Challenges at mainstream schools

Mainstream schools face many problems related to the education of SEN designated children

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Challenges at special needs schools

Special needs schools do not have optimal conditions to support the education of SEN designated children

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Insufficient external support to schools

External support to schools related to education of children with diverse needs is insufficient

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Conclusions

Although the Learning Makes Sense survey data reflect mostly the views of school staff on how their own school is ready to educate children with diverse needs and what other problems they experience in this process, they also indicate the presence of systemic barriers on the part of the state education policies. These relate mostly to insufficient (or inadequately defined) financing, understaffed support services (e.g. teaching assistants or professional staff), inadequate equipment and spaces, and also weak professional and methodological support provided to teachers and schools. When conditions for educating children with special educational needs are inadequate, it eventually impacts negatively on the quality of education provided to these children, and furthermore, it significantly worsens the education process for all children at schools.

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Selected supporting measures in education

Pedagogical assistants

The issue with the role of pedagogical assistants at schools is not just about their insufficient numbers

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Training and development of teachers and professional staff

The pre-service training of prospective teachers and in-service training of current teachers and professional staff is certainly an important part of the education system with a significant impact on its overall quality. Different factors play a role in the decision of each individual to join the pre-service training of teachers, while the overall attractiveness of the teaching profession ranks among the important ones. Both international research and qualitative data in the Learning Makes Sense project indicate that in Slovakia, the overall attractiveness of the teaching profession is relatively low due to the inadequate salaries and low social recognition of teachers. A relative scarcity of applicants for various teacher education programmes at higher education institutions means that in fact all applicants are admitted, i.e. also applicants with insufficient knowledge and skills gained from their prior studies, or applicants whose personality is not suitable for this type of work. Higher education institutions for the pre-service training of prospective teachers react differently to such diversity of admitted students. According to students themselves, pre-service teacher training is mostly focused on providing knowledge. However, students have fewer opportunities to practice their theoretical knowledge and to gain relevant teaching skills through teaching internships or classroom modelling during their higher education studies. Upon completion of a teacher education programme, not all graduates find their jobs within the Slovak education system. Schools try to hire the best teachers, and in practice not all the graduates from teacher education programmes find such a position. At the same time, for several school subjects or in certain localities, school principals have nobody to choose from. Schools could terminate jobs for teachers showing a low quality of teaching, but this does not actually happen, because it is difficult to prove low teaching quality. Also, schools can seek to professionally develop their teachers and professional staff. According to Learning Makes Sense survey findings, one of the main problems in the current in-service teacher training system is that it motivates teachers and professional staff (with salary bonuses) to attend various approved further education programmes. Yet it does not follow up on them, nor reward teachers if they gained any important skills and actually applied them at their school.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the following sections:

Attractiveness of teacher profession

Few would like to become teachers

Pre-service training of teachers at higher education institutions

Unexploited potential of higher education institutions to prepare prospective teachers well

Hiring and dismissing teachers

Hiring and dismissing teachers as an unexploited opportunity

Professional development

Professional development of teachers and professional staff and its challenges

Conclusions

The quality of an education system largely depends on whether teachers are motivated, qualified and rewarded professionals. Equally important is their ability to recognise learners' talents, their mastering of a wide variety of teaching methods, and ability to select the optimal method for every learner in

co-operation with other teachers and professional staff at schools. According to Learning Makes Sense survey findings, teacher training programmes achieve this objective to only a limited degree. Although in-service teacher training could, to some extent, compensate for the shortcomings of the pre-service training, the survey findings uncovered various doubts related to the in-service training system and its actual contribution to teachers and professionals gaining relevant knowledge and skills for their work at schools. In order that the education system should become a quality and accessible public service providing a basic educational standard to all individuals from early childhood, then the professional training, development and support for people running this system needs to be one of the cornerstones of education reform.

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Attractiveness of teacher profession

Hardly anyone wants to be a teacher

The quality of the educational system largely depends on the quality of the teachers themselves; their professional knowledge, skills and values, and also their personality profile. It is therefore essential to attract the most talented, passionate and responsible people to the teaching profession. It is equally important to create conditions that will entice them to stay. From this point of view, it is crucial to discuss the topic of the attractiveness of the teaching profession. The findings of international surveys and the qualitative data of the *Learning Makes Sense* project in this regard suggest that the teacher's salary is the most important aspect of the attractiveness of the teaching profession, and that this is critically low in Slovakia. These data point to a potential correlation between low salary and the attrition of education graduates or current teachers towards other professions. Negative stereotypes of teachers, according to which they have too much free time and the quality of their work is low, do not contribute towards elevating the social status of the teaching profession either.

The results of the [quantitative and qualitative data](#) analysis of the *Learning Makes Sense* project are presented in detail in the following sections:

Teacher salaries

The teaching profession is socially and financially underappreciated

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Teacher attrition

Teacher attrition towards other professions is significant

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Job responsibilities of teachers

Skewed images of the teaching profession do not reflect the difficulty of its responsibilities

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Personal and professional expectations

The teaching profession is associated with unrealistic social expectations

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Conclusion

In addition to educating students, teachers are responsible for numerous other activities. Quality education and the fulfilment of the additional responsibilities require a broad spectrum of knowledge, skills and socio-psychological competencies. These high demands and expectations are, however, not met with a corresponding level of salary and social recognition. It is the reality of low salaries and low social standing that turns young, talented and passionate people who would otherwise have considered teaching as their future vocation away. It also motivates current teachers to consider transferring to a different profession. This current state therefore negatively affects the quality of human resources in the teaching profession over the long term. In today's world of rapid technological advancement

and changes to the labour market and our lifestyles, both professional and personal qualities are crucial to the ability of teachers to promptly and appropriately react to these changes, and thus contribute to the holistic development of their students.

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Pre-service training of teachers at higher education institutions

Unexploited potential of higher education institutions to prepare prospective teachers well

Teacher training at higher education institutions has a vast impact on the overall quality of teaching at schools ranging from pre-primary to secondary education. Where the quality of teacher training is concerned, it is of primary importance that the selection and admission of applicants to teacher education programmes at higher education institutions should be set up appropriately. Findings from the Learning Makes Sense qualitative data analysis show that many such programmes do not apply any selection at all and admit all applicants. Therefore, the diversity of students on teacher training programmes is very large, both in terms of their knowledge and personality, and higher education institutions for pre-service teacher training adopt various approaches to it. In some cases higher education institutions ignore these differences, while in others they lower the demands set on students, or try to develop knowledge and skills that graduates from secondary schools should have already acquired. Currently, teacher training programmes at higher education institutions are split into Bachelor and Master's degrees. However, a large proportion of teaching practice and didactics is shifted to the Master's course. Higher education graduates not coming from teacher training programmes can gain their teacher qualification through an alternative route, in so-called additional teacher training. However, a significant portion of such training is provided by higher education institutions without any accredited Bachelor or Master's teacher training programmes, and their professional capacity to provide quality teacher training is questionable. Both qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data indicate that teacher training programmes focus largely on students gaining theoretical knowledge instead of their practical teaching skills. Lecture as a method of teaching prevails on teacher training programmes at higher education institutions. Many students on teacher training programmes perceive their training to have shortcomings in the area of general or subject-based didactics, which are related to knowledge and practical skills in various teaching methods. As a topic of particular importance, many students named the inclusion of children with various disabilities, where they do not feel adequately prepared either.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the following sections:

Selection of students

"Anybody" can become a teacher

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Teacher training programmes

Teacher training programmes do not contribute to preparing graduates adequately

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Education content and methods

Education content and methods on teacher training programmes at higher education institutions do not reflect the level requested from graduates

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

High quality teachers are motivated and able to recognise learners' talents. They master a wide variety of techniques and can choose the optimal learning method for every learner, in cooperation with other experts in this field. Apart from having knowledge and skills in teaching, didactics, and the ability to customise learning for their students, high quality teachers must also be experts on the subject matter they teach. The quality of teaching is affected by many factors, while pre-service teacher training at higher education institutions is certainly among them. The Learning Makes Sense findings indicate that in Slovakia, pre-service training is mostly occupied with providing theoretical knowledge, while being least concerned with developing practical didactic and teaching skills. Unless the pre-service training changes, namely, unless the students on teacher training programmes themselves experience what quality teaching should look like, then it is hard to expect these students to actually become high quality teachers themselves.

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Hiring and dismissing teachers

Hiring and dismissing teachers as an unexploited opportunity

High expectations are put on teachers. They should be motivated and qualified professionals, and able to recognise learners' talents. They should master a wide variety of techniques, and can choose the optimal learning method for every learner, in cooperation with other experts in this field. They can acquire such knowledge and skills in higher education training, in further education, or through self-education and reflection on their own work. However, when teachers choose not to develop themselves, school management can use at least two measures to increase the quality of teaching. These tools are; hiring high quality teachers, and dismissing those showing a low quality of work. However, the Learning Makes Sense qualitative data analysis indicates that school managements use the potential of these tools to only a very limited degree. Usually, they select teachers only after a job interview where they cannot fully assess the personal and professional qualities of applicants. And in case the school management uncovers teaching of a very low quality at their school, they usually refrain from dismissing a particular teacher for this reason.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the following sections:

Selection of new teachers

A three-stage selection procedure vs hiring without a job interview

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Dismissing teachers with a low quality of work

In practice, dismissing teachers with a low quality of teaching is very scarce

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Conclusions

Personal and professional expectations put on teachers in pre-primary to secondary education are high. They should know and actively use a wide variety of teaching methods and customise them for individual learners and their needs. Also, they should be motivated and continuously seeking to develop their knowledge and teaching skills. However, when teachers are not interested in meeting these expectations, they contribute to a reduction in the quality of education in Slovakia. The Learning Makes Sense qualitative data indicates that school managements do not tend to use their opportunities to prevent such teachers from teaching at local schools. Often, it is not a matter of school principals' own choice, but other factors related to the education system management which contribute to it. If we give up on having high quality teachers, we give up on the holistic development of learners and preparing them to succeed in their life.

Author: Jozef Miškolci

Professional development

Professional development of teachers and professional staff and its challenges

The quality of education at pre-primary to secondary schools depends on how prepared and competent teachers and professional staff are at schools. Upon completion of their training at a secondary school or a higher education institutions aimed to provide them with competences needed for their jobs, teachers and other professionals can further develop their skills and knowledge within the system of professional development. The system of professional development in Slovakia comprises two primary elements: the career system and the further education system for teachers and professional staff at schools. However, a professional development system should include many forms of informal learning and personal development, such as mutual lesson observations by teachers, mentoring, self-study or research activities. Exploration of this professional development system should commence with questions about; who or what institutions provide it and under what conditions? what are the forms and contents of development? and what are the incentives or barriers for teachers and professional staff when it comes to participating in it? Both qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data indicate that teachers and professional staff do not necessarily gain better competences upon achieving their certification, and they often do not perform tasks with higher responsibilities in the career system. Although professional development can be provided by various institutions, the current system significantly favours the Methodological and Pedagogical Centre, despite it not being able to meet all expectations placed upon it, according to survey respondents. Among further education providers, there is a lack of the diversity and competition that could bring about higher quality and address the various educational needs of different actors. Since the further education system rewards only the completion of further education programmes accredited by the Ministry (through salary bonuses), informal professional development is inevitably being edged out. Although the Learning Makes Sense survey findings show that the main motivation for teachers and professional staff to attend further education programmes is primarily their own interest in the particular field, although external motivation in the form of salary bonuses is very important and affects the number and selection of courses completed. The main barrier for teachers to attending various professional development activities is a lot of other work at school or an extensive workload. For the professional staff and teachers in vocational education and training, the main barrier is the lack of relevant supply of further education programmes.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) is examined in more detail in the following sections:

Career system

The current career system does not guarantee the professional development of teachers and professional staff

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Providers of professional development programmes

The Methodological and Pedagogical Centre has a preferential position in the area of professional development for teachers and professional staff at schools

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Further education

The system of further education edges out informal education of teachers and professional staff

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Motivation for professional development

Salary bonuses form an important incentive for professional development of teachers and professional staff

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Barriers to professional development

Teachers and professional staff face many barriers to their professional development

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Conclusions

Professional development of teachers and professional staff is a complex system of programmes and activities serving to enhance their professional competences and knowledge and are provided for by various institutions at varying quality. The state should monitor to what extent the system achieves its objectives. Unfortunately, the current set-up of the professional development system is such that, with salary bonuses, it motivates merely the “completion” of the education programmes. It does not reward at all if the participants gain any particular competence or if they actually use their knowledge and skills gained in practice. Up until the end of the 2018/2019 school year, there was no guarantee that, following certification and progression through the career stages, the teachers and professional staff demonstrated improved professional competence and knowledge, or indeed actually used them in practice. So the professional development system is now facing a challenge to ensure that teachers and professional staff acquire cutting edge scientific knowledge and the competence needed for their work. Only if teachers and professional staff develop in their personal and professional life can they keep pace with developments in society and encourage their learners’ motivation, curiosity, willingness to experiment and discover new information and relationships, and develop their own personality.

Author: Jozef Miškolci

Education content and methods

When development domains in student learning from pre-primary to tertiary education are considered, the highest systemic and targeted focus is placed on knowledge in various school subjects. However, insufficient attention is given to the holistic personal development of students. The Learning Makes Sense findings indicate that at schools, less attention is paid to developing the personal characteristics of students (motivation to work and study, communication, entrepreneurship, creativity, etc.), along with ethical behaviour, active citizenship, critical thinking and learning in context.

Analyses of the findings also show differences among schools with various school founders, and between various educational stages, as previously indicated in interviews carried out in the Learning Makes Sense data collection. Based on the data analysis, one of the main findings is that kindergartens and special primary schools tend to create conditions for the holistic personal development of children. However, primary and secondary schools focus their attention on attaining literacies (reading and financial), according to school principals. Secondary school students participating in the questionnaire survey confirmed that secondary schools place emphasis mostly on knowledge in their school subjects, adding that they do not consider the knowledge provided to be up-to-date. Differences exist between various higher education institutions and also in what higher education institutions abroad focus on. The Learning Makes Sense survey findings reveal that while respondents from private higher education institutions perceive that their school develops them in domains such as motivation and learning to learn, at public higher education institutions emphasis is put on knowledge and mathematical and logical thinking. At higher education institutions abroad meanwhile, respondents claim their school develops their abilities to learn in context and across various disciplines, and to think critically and accept diversity.

The education content, and its holistic and up-to-date approach (or lack of therein) in secondary and tertiary education, is also reflected in the responses of HR professionals. They expressed their views on how schools prepare their students in relation to employers' requirements from prospective employees, and based on that, they also assessed school graduates. Employees with low, middle and high qualifications only partially fulfil the requirements of employers. Moreover, they fall furthest below expectations in precisely those domains which are most demanded (motivation to work and learn, ability to learn). Most job applicants actually meet the formal education criteria, yet employers put the lowest emphasis on that in the hiring process.

The learning environment quality affects the ability to develop a broad range of skills and competences. The data from the Learning Makes Sense survey indicate that at all education levels, the prevailing teaching method is lecture, together with a discussion about the topic, according to a responding teacher. In the survey, secondary school students noted that another frequent teaching method is dictating notes. Higher education students responded that their teachers also read from textbooks aloud in classes. Active teaching methods are only applied to a limited degree, despite such approaches making learning content more attractive to students and easing their learning. According to teachers at kindergartens and the first four years of primary schools, experimental and exploratory activities carried out by children were often preferred. However, even at these education levels, lecturing as a teaching method is prevalent. When teaching methods are explored, teachers mostly responded that their students work in small groups, but this runs contrary to the finding that lecture and discussion about a topic are the most preferred teaching methods, indicating a preference for teacher-centred approaches. Teachers at primary and secondary level education who apply active learning methods and student group work reported several challenges and barriers to this approach. A frequent barrier perceived is a lack of time for more complex activities, related to 45-minute school classes and the impossibility of teaching in longer blocs. They also experience a lack of methodological and professional support in their own experiments with new teaching methods. Excursion, as a teaching form, is used by teachers at kindergartens and secondary schools. Despite the various education levels differing in their further use of excursion outcomes, teachers see it as a chance to link the education content with the world beyond the school gates. Apart from excursions, at secondary schools and higher education institutions, internships are a tool to link education with practice. Most

internships undertaken by students form a compulsory part of their studies. Although only a small proportion of surveyed students participated in voluntary internships, they tended to perceive internships more positively than their peers who completed compulsory internships.

The teaching methods applied and focusing attention on a broad range of knowledge and developing literacies have an impact on methods for assessing learners. In the Learning Makes Sense questionnaire, teachers claimed that to assess the knowledge and skills attained by learners, they mostly use announced written tests or oral evaluation at the board. Using these tools, they are mainly assessing memorised knowledge, and in the case of well compiled tests, also the degree to which students can apply their knowledge. Such an approach to knowledge and skills assessment is in line with the student development domains mostly focused on by schools – acquiring knowledge in school subjects and basic competences. One positive finding is that almost one in four teachers also assess students based on presentation of school projects. These form a part of school-leaving exams at some secondary schools, aiming not only to assess their subject-based knowledge, but also students' ability to apply specific knowledge in solving a complex task. Portfolios are only rarely used by primary and secondary school teachers, as confirmed by secondary school students. Paradoxically, despite student assessment at schools being mostly based on memorised knowledge, the students themselves responded in the Learning Makes Sense survey that they are satisfied with the way they are being assessed at schools. It can be argued that these students do not have experience with any other knowledge checks and student assessment methods, because the methods currently applied have prevailed for several generations.

Findings from the analysis of [qualitative and quantitative Learning Makes Sense data](#) are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Education content in pre-primary to tertiary education

Education content focuses on acquiring knowledge and basic competences, yet it does not concentrate on overall personal development, active citizenship nor ethical behaviour of students

Presenting the learning content

Instead of creating a learning environment for systematic learning and exploration across disciplines, the lecture as a teaching method prevails at schools and students are passive recipients of information

Conclusions

The content of education is not set up in such a way that would enable learners to gain important knowledge and develop the skills they need at the same time. The learning environments do not support active exploration, nor do they develop critical thinking, ethical behaviour, creativity, co-operation or active citizenship. The education content and teaching methods mostly focus on acquiring a set of subject-based knowledge at primary and grammar schools, or knowledge in a specific field of study at secondary schools and higher education institutions. The development of soft skills, critical thinking, creativity, co-operation, ethical behaviour and active citizenship is not systematic, and only a small proportion of schools consider it a priority. The focus on acquiring isolated pieces of knowledge is further strengthened by the teaching methods applied at schools, where students are mostly passive recipients of information. The underdevelopment of skills such as; learning strategies, communication and co-operation with other people, openness to change, resilience, problem solving, active citizenship and ethical behaviour, can consequently form a barrier to nurturing a successful personal, civic and work life. A variety of skills and personal characteristics, rather than isolated pieces of knowledge, are a prerequisite for creating a vision for one's own life and exploring routes to its fulfilment. This is the reason why education content, teaching methods and assessment approaches should change in such a way that they contribute to complex personal development, and develop the knowledge and skills conducive to a meaningful life.

Authors: Petra Fridrichová and Stanislav Lukáč

Education content in pre-primary to tertiary education

The content of education mostly focuses on acquiring a body of knowledge and basic literacies. However, it doesn't support holistic development of learners' personalities, active citizenship, or ethical behaviour

The content of education at individual educational stages is neither designed nor implemented in a way which would support the holistic development of learners' personalities. Most school principals participating in the *Learning Makes Sense* questionnaire survey place emphasis on developing subject-based knowledge (or knowledge related to learning areas in the case of kindergartens). In the case of primary and secondary schools, among the five areas most emphasised by principals are reading comprehension and financial literacy. Neither personal characteristics, motivation, nor healthy lifestyle are among the preferred areas for learners' development in primary, secondary and tertiary education in Slovakia. These findings are also confirmed by students surveyed in secondary and tertiary education. However, the *Learning Makes Sense* survey data indicate differences between the various educational stages (mainly between kindergartens and other schools) and between individual school founders. This is valid also for higher education institutions (HEIs). Principals at kindergartens, special needs kindergartens and primary schools reported similar educational priorities (co-operation of learners, ethical behaviour, etc.). The *Learning Makes Sense* survey data suggests there are differences among students at various HEIs as concerns which educational domains they perceive as being focused on by their institutions. Students at private HEIs reported that their studies develop their motivation, ability to learn, entrepreneurship and initiative more often than other students. The *Learning Makes Sense* questionnaire survey also examined differences between tertiary students in Slovakia and abroad. As far as educational domains being developed during tertiary studies are concerned, the largest differences between HEI students in Slovakia and abroad were reported as follows: ability to learn in context and across disciplines, critical thinking and acceptance of diversity.

Business HR professionals added their own views regarding the holistic and up-to-date content of education. They stated that applicants (low, middle and highly skilled staff) match up to only a limited set of required skills. Paradoxically, applicants are most deficient in those skills that employers require the most (such as motivation to study and work, and ability to learn). On the other hand, most applicants match the formal education criteria, which is the least important factor for employers.

Findings from the analysis of [quantitative and qualitative data](#) in the *Learning Makes Sense* survey regarding educational content and methods at higher education institutions are described in detail in the following chapters:

In schools the emphasis is placed upon subject-based knowledge and reading comprehension

At all educational stages, the greatest emphasis is placed upon subject-based knowledge and reading comprehension, while holistic personal development is not considered to be a priority at schools

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Education content in tertiary education

Students at Slovak higher education institutions are not being developed in a complex way

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Conclusions

The content of education as it is currently defined and implemented at all educational stages does not support complex personal development. The greatest emphasis is placed upon acquiring a body of isolated subject-based knowledge, while learning in context and analytical and critical thinking are less emphasised. Respondents (principals and students) reported that learners' personal development, healthy lifestyle and active citizenship are less prioritised than acquiring knowledge. If we claim that holistic personal development should be an educational goal at every educational stage, then it is necessary to balance knowledge acquisition with its application in order to succeed in personal, civic, and professional life. This requires education content that will enable learners to acquire the knowledge, skills and competences needed to find a job matching one's potential and interests. At the same time, education should stimulate the motivation to study and work, which is a prerequisite for career progress. If education has a narrow focus, then it does not develop learners' personalities in various aspects, so learners have to develop them elsewhere. Furthermore, they perceive that their school did not develop them in the domains needed for life. As a consequence, people tend to assign education a lower value and demand it less.

Author: Petra Fridrichová

Presenting the learning content

Instead of creating a learning environment at schools where purposeful learning and research takes place across various disciplines, many teachers design settings where students are mostly passive recipients of information

Developing a broad range of skills, competences and knowledge requires the establishing of proper conditions for such development. Analysis of quantitative data in the *Learning Makes Sense* survey indicates that at all educational stages, lecture as a teaching method prevails, together with discussion about a topic. Secondary school students participating in the *Learning Makes Sense* survey also reported that their teachers often dictate notes to them in class. Higher education students participating in the survey also reported that their teachers, as well as dictating notes, also read aloud from textbooks in lectures. Active teaching methods are being used to only a limited extent both at higher education institutions (HEIs) and secondary and primary schools, despite the fact that they appeal to students more and enable them to grasp the learning content faster. Experimental and exploratory activities carried out by children were often preferred by teachers at kindergartens and at the 1st stage of primary schools, although lecture as a teaching method is frequent at these stages too. The dominant position of lecturing as a teaching method was reported by teachers at the 2nd stage of primary schools. Most teachers reported that they often organise teaching as work in small groups. Another frequent teaching method is frontal instruction. Teachers applying active teaching methods and group work stated they have to overcome various problems and barriers. Teachers at kindergartens and secondary schools also make use of various excursions, with the aim of linking the educational content with practice, providing contact with real life, and learning in context. In tertiary education, connecting instruction with practice is also important in order to develop various skills and competences, and to ease learning. Only a small proportion of students participate in internships at service providers. This mainly applies to full-time students in specific study fields (e.g. medicine, education) and they are mostly scheduled for the master level. Most internships are compulsory. Although only a small proportion of students surveyed participated in voluntary internships, they tended to perceive internships more positively than their peers who completed compulsory internships.

Findings from the analysis of [quantitative and qualitative data](#) in the *Learning Makes Sense* survey regarding the educational content and methods at higher education institutions are described in detail in the following chapters:

Teaching methods and techniques at kindergartens, primary and secondary schools, including special needs schools

Passive teaching methods prevail over active ones at all educational stages, including special education

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Teaching methods and techniques at higher education institutions

The extent and quality of teaching methods and provided practice are inadequate

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Conclusions

The teaching methods used for presenting the content of education should be in line with overall educational goals. Currently, as indicated by the *Learning Makes Sense* survey, passive teaching methods prevail at most schools. However, these methods neither motivate lifetime learning, nor do

they develop learners' acquisition of efficient learning strategies. Technological progress, digitalisation and the rapid pace of innovation in both everyday and professional life place expectations on individuals to be able to learn constantly, and be open to all new challenges. However, instruction at schools at all educational stages is dominated by teaching methods that provide students with ready-to-use knowledge. As a result, students do not learn how to search for information they could use in life, apply their existing knowledge, create new knowledge, or solve problems by themselves or in teams. With the prevailing teaching methods, including lecturing and dictating notes with frontal teaching or individual work, students neither acquire various learning strategies, nor do they improve their teamwork skills. However, these are precisely the skills that employers request from any type of job applicant.

Author: Petra Fridrichová

Education openness, flexibility and permeability

The state should guarantee equal access to quality education. Education should be available to everyone, and the education path of each individual should be formed solely by his/her abilities and interests. To mine the potential of each learner, the education system must be capable of addressing any disabilities and eliminating sufficiently early any risk of possible failure. Only then can education actually become an opportunity for each individual, and enable them to lead a successful and meaningful life.

Almost anyone can be admitted to a university today, but access to early childhood education and care programmes is limited

Everyone should have access to early childhood education and care programmes, and these should help all children start on an equal footing when they later commence their schooling. Various research findings confirm that if children participate in these programmes, it has a positive effect on their future learning. However, no attention is placed on programmes for children aged below 3 in Slovakia, and the state cannot guarantee access to pre-primary education even for those who are willing to participate in it. Many children remain in front of the kindergarten gates, as confirmed by the *Learning Makes Sense* questionnaire survey. Almost 50% of kindergarten principals surveyed stated that demand for places in their school outnumbered vacant capacity in the school year 2017/2018. Introducing compulsory pre-primary education for children aged 5 and above contributed to the pressure for capacity increase, although the risk of insufficient capacity remains.

While people have to “fight” for a place in a kindergarten, vacant places at secondary schools and universities significantly exceed the number of potential applicants. In 2018, vacant places at secondary schools exceeded the number of primary school graduates by 15,000. Vacant places for full-time and part-time studies at universities exceeded the number of secondary school graduates by 20%. An extremely high and still increasing number of secondary school graduates heading for universities abroad also contributes to vacant places at universities. The proportion of university students from Slovakia studying abroad is 17%, while the OECD average is 2%.¹

Selection of students is spreading at lower education stages, while it is non-existent where it would be legitimate

Upon completing education at primary school, young people should have a wide choice of education paths. In most European countries young people are tracked into various education paths at the age of 14 to 16 years. In Slovakia however, tracking is present at the age of 11. Upon completing year 5 at primary school, some pupils leave for the 8-year grammar school. However, research findings show that early tracking of students does not lead to significant gains for those being tracked into premium education, and causes huge losses for those remaining in the non-premium tracks. The remaining pupils lose positive models and the motivation to work harder, because the school environment deteriorates after the best performing pupils have left.

Selection procedures are applied early, but are not applied later when they would be legitimate. The transition of pupils after year 9 at primary school to secondary schools more closely resembles recruitment than selection. Softening admission criteria is even more apparent in the transition to tertiary education. While in 2005 less than a third of applications was accepted without entrance exams, in 2018 this proportion rose to 61%. The absence of entrance exams probably deters the more ambitious applicants. In the questionnaire survey, more than 80% of students from Slovakia studying at universities abroad claimed that the decision to abolish entrance exams is lowering the quality of universities in Slovakia. Teachers point also to a reduction in the quality of universities, yet in addition they attribute it to the insufficient abilities of students. In the questionnaire survey, almost 70% of

¹ Table B6.3. Mobility patterns of foreign and international students. In *Education at a Glance 2018: OECD Indicators*. Paris : OECD Publishing, 2018. Available at: https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/education-at-a-glance-2018_eag-2018-en#page232

teachers ranked the low quality of students among the five factors that worsen the quality of education. However, qualitative data point to the lack of systemic communication between secondary schools and universities in preparing students for their university studies. The criticism directed at the abilities of university applicants is related to teachers' expectations. With the new millennium, university studies in Slovakia opened up to a broader group of students, but this process did not involve the diversification of universities this necessitated. Most universities continued to offer mostly academically-oriented study programmes.

There are groups of people with no access to higher education stages

The state should guarantee equal access to quality education, and the education path of each individual should be formed solely by his/her abilities and interests. However, not everyone has access to higher education, with learners with disabilities and social disadvantages facing the most difficulties. Compared to other countries, significantly fewer people go through higher education than their parents.²

To a large extent, this relates to people living in social exclusion. Calculations by the Education Policy Institute and Value for Money Unit show that more than a third of pupils from excluded Roma localities finished their compulsory education without attaining a full basic education, and fewer than half continued on further studies in the school year 2017/18.³ In secondary education, these students attend mostly practical schools and special vocational schools for students with mental disabilities, or they attend mainstream vocational schools. However, they often attend 2-year study programmes offering no professional qualifications, and this significantly decreases their chances of finding a job. The proportion of students from socially disadvantaged backgrounds (SDB) at universities is even lower than at secondary schools. In the school year 2017/18, only 8% of young people aged 19–23 years receiving material benefits attended universities. This proportion is 4 times lower than their total proportion of the population.⁴ Less than 1% of Roma have a university degree. Support for students coming from excluded Roma localities is reduced to needs-based scholarships serving to partially eliminate the financial barriers. However, they do not receive support in other important areas, and their families and relatives can only help them to a limited degree, as they themselves lack experience with university studies.

Similarly, the education paths of people with disabilities differ from the majority population. While children with disabilities comprise 11% of all primary school pupils, at secondary schools their proportion drops below 7%. This indicates that a significant proportion of children with disabilities do not continue their studies at secondary schools. This is mainly the case for children with a diagnosed mental disability. The *Learning Makes Sense* survey findings indicate that transition to secondary school can also pose problems for children diagnosed with autism, multiple disabilities or sensory disabilities. Transition to secondary schools is further complicated by the limited access to career advice. A quarter of special primary schools do not provide it at all. Secondary school choice is thus driven mostly by the openness and accessibility of particular schools to the education of students with disabilities, rather than by their own abilities and interests. Physical barriers in school buildings pose a particular problem, along with the lack of teaching assistants and personal assistants for learners with disabilities, and the inadequate competences of teachers in working with these learners, a shortcoming which is not compensated for by methodological support for teachers. It is alarming that a significant proportion of children with disabilities attend programmes without a school-leaving exam (28%), and similarly to Roma children, this lowers their chances of entering the labour market.

² OECD. Table A4.1. Intergenerational mobility in education. In *Education at a Glance 2015: OECD Indicators*. Paris : OECD Publishing, 2015. Available at: https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/education-at-a-glance-2015_eag-2015-en#page80

³ Spending review for the groups at risk of poverty and social exclusion. Interim report. Bratislava: Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic and the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, 2019. Available at: <https://www.minedu.sk/revizia-vydavkov-na-skupiny-ohrozene-chudobou-alebo-socialnym-vylucenim-2019/>

⁴ Spending review for the groups at risk of poverty and social exclusion. Interim report. Bratislava: Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic and the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, 2019. Available at: <https://www.minedu.sk/revizia-vydavkov-na-skupiny-ohrozene-chudobou-alebo-socialnym-vylucenim-2019/>

Only a small proportion of students with disabilities continue their studies at a university. In 2018, some 7,000 students with disabilities attended programmes with a school-leaving exam at secondary schools, while only a thousand such students studied at universities. The *Learning Makes Sense* survey findings indicate that despite partial positive measures at many universities, there are still physical barriers present and they limit access to university education for people with disabilities. Students with sensory disabilities or arm disabilities also face barriers related to IT systems, and have limited access to academic literature and other materials.

Low state support hinders the process of eliminating barriers, because public universities receive only half of the subsidies requested for students with special needs (SEN). Also, specific support measures for individual groups of students with SEN are not defined. Having such a definition is particularly important, since people serving as SEN support co-ordinators at universities have various backgrounds, do not attend training in this field, and often perform this task beyond the scope of their regular duties and for low financial compensation. Yet their role is extremely important in providing guidance to teachers. There are also shortcomings in training and support for university teachers in teaching SEN designated students.

The education system introduces compensatory measures instead of placing emphasis on prevention

The education system should help equalise opportunities and compensate for disadvantages as early as possible, thus eliminating or significantly reducing the risk of future failure. Currently, it addresses the needs of people at risk too late, and applies compensatory rather than preventive measures. The system contains various costly and not always effective measures which have been introduced due to inadequate prevention at preceding education stages.

An example is the introduction of preparatory classes (“zero classes”) aiming to help children with little or no access to early childhood education and care programmes. While the intention to compensate for disadvantages can be appreciated, available data suggest that learners from the preparatory classes still experience failure later at school. Moreover, the year spent in a preparatory class is included in the period of compulsory education and students who repeated a year at primary school frequently finish their studies before they complete year 9 at school. Consequently, state education policies address this by offering courses to complete education at primary school and they are provided mostly by secondary vocational schools offering 2-year vocational programmes. In the end, these students often finish their education path without achieving any work qualification at all. However, their chances of entering higher education would have been higher if the schools they attended had addressed their learning needs more effectively using a wide range of support measures.

Findings from the analysis of [qualitative and quantitative data](#) from the *Learning Makes Sense project* related to **education openness, flexibility and permeability** are examined in more detail and in the context of other data in the following sections:

At the doors of compulsory education or an (un)sure start

Entry to compulsory education or an (un)equal start

Transition to lower secondary education

Transition to secondary education

Transition to higher education

Transition from the 1st stage to 2nd stage at universities

Author: Katarína Vančíková

At the doors of compulsory education

At the doors of compulsory education or (un)sure start

Scientific evidence from neuroscience, biology and psychology suggests early childhood to be a period of great opportunity as well as risk. Research findings have repeatedly confirmed that children can benefit from participation in early childhood education and care programmes (ECEC). These programmes can have a significant positive impact on their success in further education. Access to ECEC is of crucial importance for children from socially disadvantaged backgrounds (SDB), as well as children with disabilities or high risk development. They present a great opportunity for them to start on an equal footing with their peers at the commencement of compulsory education. However, the benefits of ECEC programmes largely depend on their quality. Several countries, aiming to improve their ECEC, have adopted an integrated system approach to provide continuity of services along with complex help and support for all children. Slovakia resists this trend. It preserves its internally fragmented system, featuring several governmental ministries as coordinators of individual programmes, thereby lacking the necessary coherence and co-operation. Such fragmentation affects mainly the most vulnerable groups of children, who cannot benefit from early childhood education and care programmes in the way their peers can. Fragmentation into several sectors is mainly reflected in the non-systemic governance of early childhood education and care programmes for children aged below 3. In Slovakia, these programmes are not perceived as being a basic prerequisite of quality pre-primary education. In most countries, the ECEC system covers care of children from their birth up to the start of their schooling. In our country, attention is paid to pre-primary education covering mostly children aged 3 and over. However, ECEC programmes for younger children are on the margins. In public discourse, nurseries are an important topic, reflecting the rising demand of parents for institutional care for their children. There are not many options for them. Capacity in kindergartens in several towns and municipalities struggles to accommodate even the older children, and there are only a few public nurseries. At private nurseries, fees exceed the state subsidy parents are entitled to receive for this purpose, and due to the so-called "Nursery Act", these nurseries are still few in number.

The fact that care for children below 3 years of age is not perceived to be a part of the ECEC system is reflected in its legal definition as a social service. Moreover, nurseries are even defined as an ambulant social service. The legal regulation of these facilities relates mainly to safety, child protection and hygiene. Nobody monitors pedagogic activities with children and no methodological guidance is provided. The fact that early childhood care for children below 3 is neglected is also mirrored in the limited access to these programmes for the most vulnerable groups – children with disabilities or from socially disadvantaged backgrounds. Children with disabilities and their families can participate in the early intervention system, which has been developed over a longer period of time. Due to limited funding, and the low regional coverage and availability of information, many families face difficulties in accessing these services. Socially excluded families living in poverty have no opportunity to participate in an ECEC programme for children aged below 3. Institutional care is neither a solution nor an option for these families, and a portfolio of programmes for the youngest children is not prepared for them.

There are also challenges concerning access to pre-primary education programmes designed mainly for children aged 3 or over. Low enrolment of children in kindergartens provides the evidence. Slovakia is far from the EU 2020 target aiming at a 95% participation rate in pre-primary education for children aged 4 and over, up until their commencement of compulsory schooling. In 2017, Slovakia had 76% of children of this age in kindergartens. Calculations performed by the Learning Makes Sense team point to significant regional differences. In the regions of Košice and Prešov, the situation is critical and is mainly caused by the long-term low participation rate of Roma children in these programmes. Only a third of them attend kindergartens.

This low participation rate in pre-primary education is also caused by inadequate capacity in kindergartens, and this problem has not been addressed for the long term. Even if parents are willing to enrol their children at a kindergarten, not all children are admitted. Lack of capacity gives rise to

discriminatory practices in the admission of children in certain cases. Primarily affected are children with no permanent residence in the respective municipality or urban area where the kindergarten is located, and children with unemployed parents. Such circumstances also lower the chances of children with disabilities being admitted. The Learning Makes Sense team estimates that more than half of these children are not admitted to kindergartens. Their proportion of the total population of children in kindergartens is ten times lower than their proportion in primary schools. The kindergarten principal has the legal right to refuse admission of such a child if conditions in the kindergarten are not appropriate. However, there are no specific criteria to assess which conditions are appropriate and which not. Therefore, kindergarten principals make their decision based on their own judgement. In this context, the Learning Makes Sense questionnaire survey provides interesting insights. Only a fifth of respondents from kindergartens considers their own kindergarten ready to educate children with disabilities. Respondents listed the following main challenges in the education of SEN designated children: insufficient conditions for a customised approach due to a high number of children in classes; lack of teaching assistants and professional staff; physical barriers in school buildings; lack of funds to address the needs of SEN designated children and teachers unprepared for work with these children. Inadequate conditions for educating children with disabilities often result in mainstream kindergartens refusing to admit them. From those admitted to kindergartens, two thirds attend special needs kindergartens. Yet there are many districts in Slovakia with no such institutions. At the same time, many special needs kindergartens face similar problems with lack of funds and staff.

Also, it is doubtful whether kindergartens are ready to educate children from SDB. Findings from both qualitative and quantitative surveys suggest that kindergartens do not have the conditions for a customised approach to children and the provision of the support services necessary. Another challenge is the relative inability of kindergarten staff to work with children speaking other languages. This may be the reason why a quarter of kindergarten teachers and principals believe that children with a different mother tongue should be educated in special needs classes or schools. Low participation in pre-primary education of children from excluded localities can also be caused by the lack of programmes focusing on liaison with their parents. Parental expenditure on pre-primary education and its impact on access to education needs to be tackled as well. There are several supporting measures targeted at assisting children from low-income families. However, under the current system, kindergarten attendance (especially for younger children) is not free of charge. Firstly, the income threshold for these families is set too low, and secondly, the supporting measures do not cover all expenditure related to kindergarten attendance. Another important barrier to access is the significant distance to kindergartens. At time of the survey, this barrier was relevant for a fifth of excluded Roma localities.

Analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data from the *Learning Makes Sense* survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Importance of early childhood education and care

Why attention should be paid to early childhood education and care

[Available only in Slovak](#)

ECEC system is fragmented

The early childhood education and care system is significantly fragmented

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Care in early years is neglected

Early childhood care of children aged below 3 is overlooked. Is that a problem?

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Low access to pre-primary education

Pre-primary education is not accessible to all

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

The state should guarantee equal access to quality education. Countries taking this goal seriously place significant emphasis on increasing access to, and quality of, early childhood education and care programmes. The quality of these programmes is influenced by the ability of the ECEC system to address the complex needs of all children and their families, and consequently help improve life chances for everyone. Therefore, particular attention is placed on creating an integrated system which is sufficiently well coordinated that children and their families can access all services they need, even before they reach the age of 3. Integrated ECEC systems provide for continuous and targeted child development, from birth to the commencement of schooling. In such systems, early childhood care programmes for children aged below 3 are not only a service designed for parents pursuing their jobs or studies. Their role is also to address the various needs these children and their families might have, including those caused by disabilities or social disadvantage. Integrated ECEC systems provide a seamless transition to pre-primary education, which is perceived to be a basic prerequisite for successful schooling. Therefore it is accessible to all, and in many countries there is a legal entitlement to this service. If public policies cannot create opportunities for all children to participate in ECEC programmes, then this indicates little attention is being paid to equal education opportunity in that country.

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Entry to compulsory education

Entry to compulsory education or an (un)equal start

Age is not the only prerequisite for a child to start their schooling in year 1 at primary school. The commencement of compulsory schooling in Slovakia is conditional upon the readiness for school of a child. Enrolment data to year 1 suggest that almost one in seven children do not comply with this prerequisite, and in regions with the lowest participation in pre-primary education, this proportion is even higher. These children receive an additional year to improve in domains pertaining to their readiness for school. However, the system provides two tracks for improving the child's readiness for school. The majority of children aged 6 not yet ready for schooling receive a recommendation for a 1-year postponement of compulsory schooling, and would start their schooling at the age of 7. Children from socially disadvantaged backgrounds are almost automatically tracked into preparatory "zero" classes. Upon entry to a preparatory "zero" class, they start their compulsory schooling. Preparatory "zero" classes can significantly improve the readiness for school of children, but their further impact on their education path and later success in life is unclear. Available data suggest that many children starting in the preparatory "zero" classes later fail in their education, and finish their compulsory education without attaining the full basic education level. Their chances of acquiring a professional qualification are therefore slim.

Enrolment in kindergartens can substantially reduce the number of children with postponed compulsory schooling or children tracked into preparatory "zero" classes. However, the potential of kindergartens remains rather unexploited here. One of the reasons is the weak co-operation with advisory and prevention centres in certain towns and municipalities, mostly due to insufficient personnel capacity and time availability at centres. Another problem is the weak co-operation between parents, teachers and the advisory and prevention centres, often resulting in biased findings about the child's readiness for school. The readiness for school of a child is also affected by the ability of a kindergarten to address the child's developmental needs. Such ability is reduced by the lack of professionals (school psychologists, SEN teachers, etc.) who could substantially contribute to higher quality diagnostics and design of support measures. However, children in Slovak kindergartens do not receive such professional support. Developing readiness for school is therefore mainly the task of kindergarten teachers, and they have to divide their attention among twenty children on average. Opportunities for a customised approach are hence rather limited, and so is the chance that the number of children with postponed schooling will decrease in the future.

Readiness for school is also checked during enrolment to year 1. The Learning Makes Sense findings suggest that schools adopt various approaches to this, and the quality of test tasks and sets varies. But their results really matter. These conclusions can determine whether the child's schooling is postponed or not, and at some schools, it can even determine whether the child is enrolled at all. Competitive selection is mostly present at schools where the demand for places exceeds capacity. Right at the start of compulsory education, some children are formally rejected.

Although readiness for school is checked at entry to year 1, the Schools Act permits for a child to be admitted, but can later on permit their schooling being postponed, meaning they have to leave the school. Qualitative data from the Learning Makes Sense suggest that children often take this very hard. Moreover, such cases can result from an erroneous readiness for school assessment, or from a failure of communication between the kindergarten, family and advisory and prevention centre. Statistics further indicate that a significant group of children repeat year 1. This is mostly experienced by children in Eastern Slovakia. The Learning Makes Sense questionnaire survey suggests that most teachers in Slovakia agree with the concept of grade repetition. Unpleasant feelings of failure can be experienced by children tracked into special needs schools in their early years of schooling. This phenomenon is more frequent in Eastern Slovakia as well.

Analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data in the *Learning Makes Sense* survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Readiness for school as a problem

Assessing readiness for school introduces elements of inequality into the system

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Preparing children for transition to schools and kindergarten shortcomings

Kindergarten shortcomings in preparing children for a seamless transition to primary schools

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Diverse practices in enrolment to year 1

Practices applied in enrolment to year 1 are not standardised

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Disappointment and failure at the start of the education path

Children have already experienced disappointment and failure when they start their education paths

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

Children in Slovakia start compulsory schooling at various ages and similarly, leave primary school at various ages. The starting point is not just determined by their age, but also by their readiness for school. Had the children who received a “red light” at entry to year 1 attended kindergarten, their chances would have been higher. This mainly concerns children that start their compulsory education in the preparatory “zero” class. The chances of reducing the numbers for postponed compulsory schooling or placements into preparatory “zero” classes is largely determined by the customised support for learners, and the engagement of professional staff or teaching assistants in kindergartens. Unless quality diagnostics and intervention is directly guaranteed by psychologists and other professionals in classrooms, the quality of co-operation with the advisory and prevention centres remains crucial. Postponement of compulsory schooling creates an objective barrier to the seamless transition to schooling. This is accentuated by the fact that such decisions are made at enrolment procedures at individual schools without using standardised procedures for assessing the readiness for school. As indicated by the *Learning Makes Sense* research findings, there are still many children experiencing failure later in their schooling, despite passing the readiness for school assessment.

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Transition to lower secondary education

Upon completing the primary education stage, children proceed to the next phase. During the next five years they should master the requirements set for lower secondary education. Learners can achieve this level of education at various school types. The Slovak school system features a significant outer differentiation of education paths. The majority of pupils complete lower secondary education at primary schools in their so-called 2nd stage. Another group of pupils leave primary school upon completion of year 8 and proceed to 5-year secondary schools, usually bi-lingual schools. Finally, there are 8-year grammar schools, to which pupils proceed upon completion of year 5 at primary school. A significant group of pupils decide on their future at the age of 11. Qualitative data from the Learning Makes Sense survey indicate that it is not only the best-performing pupils who proceed to 8-year grammar schools. However, research findings show that the early tracking of students does not lead to significant gains for those being tracked into premium education, and causes huge losses for those remaining in the non-premium tracks. The remaining pupils lose positive models and the motivation to work harder, because the school environment deteriorates after the best performing pupils have left. The school environment is not ideal even in the premium tracks. In the survey, primary school principals indicated that the outflow of pupils to 8-year grammar schools causes several problems. Apart from deteriorating learning outcomes in "T9" national testing, the attractiveness of the school diminishes, and the school environment in terms of learning and social profile in classrooms changes. Frequently, school principals have to merge classes and disrupt established student teams. Lastly, the fact that schools are competing for students in regions with an oversupply of 8-year grammar schools negatively impacts on the school-year planning process, because up until the last moment, primary school principals do not know if all pupils come back in September or not.

Regardless of whether pupils stay at primary schools or they proceed to 8-year grammar schools, their learning environments should address their developmental needs. Only then can their potential be fulfilled and developed in line with their interests and abilities. During their transition to lower secondary education they enter adolescence, and this period has significant developmental characteristics. The selection of teaching methods by teachers is particularly important, because pupils at this age need more contact with their peers, and they need to discuss, philosophise, and analyse the world around them whilst adopting their own stance to it. The learning environment should take young adolescents' desire for autonomy into account, together with their need to participate in decision-making on all issues that affect them.

The Learning Makes Sense survey findings indicate that there is a certain mismatch between these adolescents' features and the actual teaching methods applied at the 2nd stage of primary schools. Survey respondents indicate that the potential for social and peer learning is not fully exploited by schools. Moreover, despite teachers in both types of schools claiming they often speak and discuss with their students, other responses they provided, combined with the secondary school students' answers, cast doubt on whether such communication really is a two-way discussion enabling all actors to think and express themselves. Responses by teachers also indicated that teaching methods developing cognitive functions are less frequently applied in instruction. Memorising and one-way lecturing should have already disappeared at the 2nd stage of primary schools, but survey findings indicate that lecturing as a teaching method dominates both at the 2nd stage of primary schools and at 8-year grammar schools. In the questionnaire survey, students enrolled in 8-year grammar schools cited "dictating notes" among the most frequent teaching methods at their school, and reported that school does not develop them in terms of learning in context and across disciplines. The ability of our schools to address students' desire for respect and participation in decision-making is signalled by the methods of assessment they apply. Teacher responses indicate that pupils in the 2nd stage of primary schools have fewer opportunities to influence their assessment than they had during the initial four years of their studies. In the survey, students at 8-year grammar schools also expressed their dissatisfaction. Half the students surveyed are not satisfied with the assessment methods applied, and the same proportion perceive that teachers at 8-year grammar schools do not apply fair assessment to all students. A positive finding is that a slightly higher proportion of students perceive their opinion to be accepted in assessment. Still, available data do not indicate that, after transition from primary

schools, students enter an environment where they are commonly approached as partners. They experience humiliating or ridiculing here, just as they might have earlier. The adolescents' desire for autonomy is limited by few opportunities to participate in decision-making about issues at their school. More than half the students at 8-year grammar schools confirmed this experience.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative data](#) from the *Learning Makes Sense* survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Educational tracking at the start of lower secondary education

At the start of lower secondary education, ill-judged educational tracking exists

[Available only in Slovak](#)

The streaming of pupils takes place too early

We start with streaming of pupils too early

[Available only in Slovak](#)

(In)ability of schools to address developmental needs of adolescent pupils

(In)ability of schools to address developmental needs of adolescent pupils and to ease their transition to further educational levels

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

Countries with early educational tracking of pupils experience an increasing gap between them later on. School choice is also affected by social status and the economic status of their parents. There is research evidence that the later the education tracking happens, the greater the educational opportunities are for all children. There is no reliable and incontrovertible evidence showing that students in premium tracks gain more advantages from their studies. Still, 8-year grammar schools in Slovakia are popular with the general public and receive systemic support. However, 8-year grammar schools pose a problem in terms of openness and permeability of educational paths. Upon completing lower secondary education, young people should have a wide choice of learning programmes. However, if they complete it at an 8-year grammar school, they may remain locked into an academic track started at the age of 11. Transition to a premium track does not necessarily entail a transition to a learning environment better addressing the developmental needs of adolescents and developing their cognitive and personal potential. The *Learning Makes Sense* research findings rather indicate that teaching methods applied at the 2nd stage of primary schools as well as at 8-year grammar schools only partially reflect the natural needs of pupils entering a new stage in their developmental journey towards being responsible adults.

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Transition to secondary education

Schools have several roles in society. One of them is to prepare the youth for their further studies and the labour market. Therefore, the education system needs to apply efficient selection mechanisms to distribute pupils to various types of schools. While in most European countries, such selection occurs at the age of 14–16 years, in Slovakia, there is no functional selection during the transition from year 9 to secondary schools. The reason is that the “filtering” occurred much earlier, when a group of students entered the 8-year grammar schools. In the Learning Makes Sense questionnaire survey, the career advisers at schools said that students proceed to secondary schools that do not match their abilities or interests. The selection of an inappropriate school can be caused by insufficient career advice, but competition for students among schools is another factor. Vacant places at secondary schools exceed the number of pupils leaving year 9 by a quarter. In order to fill the vacancies, secondary schools relax their admission criteria.

Competition for students among secondary schools can bring about positive results in certain regions, namely in enhancing communication between primary and secondary schools. The qualitative data suggests that secondary school principals are more active in their communication with prospective applicants. Secondary schools organise open days several times a year, they present themselves at public events in their towns, and seek opportunities how to best approach young people. They seek out presentation opportunities at primary schools, and their events have become more interactive. Several research interviews indicate that secondary schools started to pay attention to the quality of career advice at primary schools, and it can be reasoned that the marketing behaviour of secondary schools can exert pressure for more intensive co-operation with schools at earlier education levels. Still, the Learning Makes Sense research findings indicate that co-operation between primary and secondary schools has not yet been fully exploited, and that it is often reduced to the participation of pupils at open day events or secondary school presentations.

Another important issue related to the transition of students to secondary schools is early school leaving. Slovakia is among the 17 European countries where the proportion of early school leavers among people aged 18–24 is below 10%. However, Slovakia experienced a worrying increase in this figure during 2009–2017. Early school leaving is an issue more relevant for some regions than others. In other words, this phenomenon is related to poverty and social exclusion. The highest prevalence of these cases can be expected in areas with the highest poverty and unemployment rates. The worst situation is therefore in regions with the highest proportion of Roma population. As confirmed in the Learning Makes Sense interviews, early school leaving is a problem mostly concerning Roma pupils from excluded Roma localities.

Early school leaving is a complex problem with various causes and risks as pertaining to pupils, schools and the education system as such. The living conditions where these young people grow up are a significant factor. Despite the causes of this problem originating from difficult living conditions, these cannot be identified as the single critical cause. Early school leaving occurs mainly as a consequence of a failing education system, where little attention is paid to addressing this phenomenon. Little attention is paid to preventive measures, resulting in the lack of early childhood care programmes for children aged below 3 from disadvantaged backgrounds and their low participation in pre-primary education. This contributes to a differing starting position for at-risk children compared to their peers when they start schooling, and they are already at risk of grade retention during compulsory education. These children often enter year 1 at the age of 7 or 8. The reason is that many of them start their schooling in the preparatory “zero” year, and some even repeat it. Multiple grade retentions at primary school are frequent especially for pupils from socially disadvantaged background. Often, these cases result in early school leaving. Both grade retention and early school leaving could be less frequent if schools addressed the learning needs of at-risk students more effectively. However, the Learning Makes Sense findings show that many school actors lack support from SEN teachers or psychologists. Survey respondents claimed that if schools had engaged more professionals, there would have been fewer early school leavers. Reducing class sizes would also help, according to survey respondents, enabling a more customised approach to learners. Although the fight against poverty is

important in preventing early school leaving, only a third of survey respondents agree that there would have been fewer early school leavers had more of them received financial support. Qualitative data from the Learning Makes Sense project suggest that school actors see the solution to this problem in more intensive work with families.

Due to the low emphasis on prevention of students failing in their education, there is a group of students leaving school without attaining basic education level. Most of these cases are in the Košice, Prešov and Banská Bystrica regions. If the education system does not compensate for the initial disadvantage of these people, they have an option to take a course to complete their basic education, the so-called second chance programme. Such courses are organised mostly by secondary vocational schools offering 2-year vocational programmes, so-called F-programmes (formerly “lower vocational schools”). The Learning Makes Sense survey results, along with available statistics, show that less than half of such schools provide this opportunity. Available data also suggest that only a small proportion of people without a completed basic education take part in the second chance programmes. Furthermore, the State School Inspection findings indicate that not all courses have the required quality. The low flexibility of this additional education poses another problem, because completing a second chance course is a prerequisite to applying for upper vocational education. The Ministry of Education prepared a draft suggesting that second chance course participants could complete their basic education while being enrolled on the study programme. However, this draft has not yet been approved. Students completing the F-programmes have very limited chances to enter the labour market. Upon completion of these programmes, they do not earn a vocational certificate, and therefore they possess no professional qualification. They leave school trained to perform simple auxiliary tasks and basic tasks in simple vocations. Moreover, in certain districts and regions, availability of 2-year F-programmes is very limited, as confirmed by primary school principals at the Learning Makes Sense project interviews. Three quarters of institutions offering 2-year F-programmes are secondary school subsidiaries located near Roma excluded localities. Perceived lack of 2-year F-programmes in certain regions can also depend on the willingness of secondary school principals to offer them. The Learning Makes Sense questionnaire survey suggests that school principals do not find it difficult to provide funds, time, spaces and staff for such studies. It rather indicates that they do not consider the offering of 2-year vocational programmes to be their priority. However, the analysis of the qualitative data suggests that schools might also opt not to provide these 2-year programmes due to weak state support, reflected in the lack of professional staff at schools.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative data](#) from the *Learning Makes Sense* survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Student admission to secondary schools

Selection procedures at secondary schools replaced by student recruitment

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Activities of secondary schools in a competitive environment

Competition for students motivates secondary schools to present their study programmes more effectively

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Early school leaving

A group of students does not complete secondary education or does not even start it

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Second chance programmes in education

Lower performing students have limited opportunities for their return to education and acquiring of a qualification

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

Schools play several important roles in society. They should develop the skills and abilities of each individual and contribute to the personal fulfilment and development of satisfied and happy people. Schools represent an important social policy tool, and to a large extent they influence labour market quality and flexibility. Selection procedures are an important tool for effectively distributing students to various school types and future professions. Excess capacity at secondary schools and the subsequent escalated competition edges out these procedures and schools cease to function as selection points, which is a legitimate and necessary function at certain education levels. Although selection by secondary schools has been replaced by recruitment of students, there are still groups of students who do not enter secondary education because they did not complete their basic education. Another group of students completes their basic education, but does not enrol at secondary school or does not complete their studies. Early school leaving is a phenomenon which requires careful attention, due to its many negative consequences for individuals and society. It aggravates economic and social imbalances in various countries, because many people leave school without having a chance to enter the labour market and live a successful personal and civic life.

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Transfer to higher education

The ratio of people with higher education in Slovakia is lower than the EU and OECD average. However, a rising trend is apparent. Many young people recognize higher education as important to success in the job market, as well as to personal growth. While the ratio of higher education graduates is increasing, the number of students at higher education institutions has been decreasing. One of the reasons is that the attrition of a large part of the student population to higher education institutions abroad is greater than the number of incoming international higher education students. The results of the *Learning Makes Sense* survey have shown that more than half of the secondary school students surveyed plan to study abroad after graduation. The responses of the higher education students already studying abroad suggest that their motivation to leave Slovakia was strong. Reasons given for leaving include the superior reputation of international higher education institutions, or the better prospects in the job market afforded by a degree from abroad. Another issue is that our students also plan to remain abroad after graduating.

The loss of students to other countries, in combination with a demographic fall, leads to the lowering of entry criteria for higher education applicants. The number of open spots at higher education institutions is higher than the number of secondary school graduates, and given that the number of students enrolled plays a significant role in the financing of higher education institutions, each school tries to meet its enrolment targets, even if it means foregoing entrance exams. The qualitative data of *Learning Makes Sense* suggest that the entry criteria at some higher education institutions are so low that they can be met by almost any applicant. The number of highly selective schools has been falling. Based on the results of the *Learning Makes Sense* survey, it can be concluded that the abolishment of entrance exams in Slovakia is perceived negatively by students who have decided to study abroad. The insufficient, or non-existent student selection process, does not just affect the reputation of our higher education institutions, it also impacts on their quality. According to higher education teachers, the low aptitude of students is one of the most significant factors negatively affecting the quality of their teaching. The results of the interview analyses suggest that some of them see the reason as being the low level and inadequacy of the secondary education curriculum. Systematic communication and collaboration between secondary schools and higher education institutions is lacking however, leading to a lack of a dialogue on mutual expectations. The perception of students as being underprepared to meet the demands of higher education studies is related to the nature of the degree programmes offered by the higher education institutions. The higher education sector has not reacted to the increasing demand for higher education graduates, and has not been able to accommodate a more diverse student population. In contrast to many higher education institutions abroad, those in Slovakia still offer predominantly academically-oriented degree programmes, and accept secondary school graduates in the expectation of enrolling only elite, academically-oriented applicants.

Low entry requirements in education can contribute to an increase in cases of prematurely terminated education. The interviewees from the *Learning Makes Sense* qualitative data collection mentioned that, because students did not pass the entrance exams, the selection process takes place during their studies. According to the most recently available data, approximately one third of students in OECD and EU countries ends their higher education without graduating. In Slovakia this ratio is slightly lower. However, our country is an exception because the majority of these students will never return to higher education and finish their degrees. The premature termination of higher education can be the result of an unsuitable choice of school, which is therefore also a reflection of poor career counselling services at secondary schools. It can also reflect the insufficient support of higher education institutions in the process of helping new students to acclimatise. Comparing the opinions of students in Slovakia with those who left to study abroad suggests that our schools are behind in many ways. The results of the *Learning Makes Sense* qualitative data analysis suggests that some higher education institutions are becoming aware of this issue, and are beginning to find ways to reduce this attrition.

While the applicant selection process can be quite tough, certain groups of people find it more difficult to obtain a higher education degree than others. These include people with a health or social disability, who must overcome many barriers on their road to higher education.

According to the results of Learning Makes Sense, only a small number of students with a health disability chooses to study at a higher education institution. In 2018 there were only seven thousand graduating from secondary schools. On undergraduate and graduate higher education programmes this number has only been around one thousand. This indicates the presence of barriers in the academic environment. The issue of creating a universally accessible environment is currently being debated, partly thanks to the higher education bill binding higher education institutions to offer support to students and applicants with special needs. However, according to the registry these constitute less than one per cent of the higher education population. The reasons for their low representation are varied, and related both to the selective nature of our education system and an inflexible social system. According to secondary data, in addition to the *Learning Makes Sense* data, it can be concluded that barriers exist also on the part of the higher education institutions, who are facing multiple challenges. In most rooms found in schools and student residences, it is not possible for a person with limited mobility to move independently without the help of others. The removal of IT barriers is also an important challenge, as well as the overall improvement of the information-communication accessibility of the academic environment. Young people with sensory or upper body physical disabilities have a genuine problem accessing information from web domains, while using the academic IT systems also remains difficult.

An encouraging finding is that Slovakia operates two special pedagogical centres supporting students with special needs, mandated by the law to serve as methodological, knowledge and coordination centres for all higher education institutions in Slovakia. The number of counselling and support centres for students with special needs at other higher education institutions is also increasing. At the moment, such centres are in operation at half of the public higher education institutions. The work of these centres or coordinators for students with special needs often affects the quality of the work of higher education teachers. According to the findings of *Learning Makes Sense*, students with special needs have varied experiences with the personal and professional quality of educators. Low awareness of the needs of individual groups of people with disabilities leads to insufficient support during tuition. However, not all teachers can utilise the advice of a coordinator, other specialists or internal methodological guidelines.

Higher education institutions cannot meet the challenges of supporting students with special needs without systematic backing. At the moment, higher education institutions receive approximately half of the budget required for securing support services. The creation of a universal academic environment remains a vision, in part due to the unresolved financing of the special education centres and coordinators for students with special needs. These have for many years lacked not just financing, but also detailed legal definition, necessary for providing the students with more appropriate aid. A binding directive is especially necessary because coordinators' job is carried out by people with different professional profiles, and some higher education institutions are not even collaborating with external counselling centres that would have provided a professional assessment for the students' special needs.

While the number of higher education graduates among people living in poverty and social exclusion is critically low, support for students coming from these environments is limited to offering social stipends, which can help to partially remove the financial barriers. However, experiences from abroad, as well as from the *Aj ty máš šancu!* [You too have a chance!] pilot programme carried out in Slovakia, suggest that these students also need other forms of support. The results of the *Learning Makes Sense* qualitative data analysis however, indicate that this topic has not yet resonated sufficiently with most higher education institutions.

The results of the quantitative and qualitative data analysis of the Learning Makes Sense project are presented in detail in the following sections:

The changes in the number of higher education graduates

The ratio of higher education graduates is increasing, but the number of students at Slovak higher education institutions is decreasing

[Available only in Slovak](#)

The loss of students to other countries

Many higher education students go abroad in pursuit of a better education, while only a small part of them wants to come back

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Enrolment of higher education students

The majority of schools do not select their students

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The reasons for studying at higher education institution

Students apply to higher education institutions not only out of interest, but also their need to gain employment

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The readiness of secondary school graduates for higher education

The lack of readiness of secondary school graduates for higher education is relative

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The premature termination of higher education

There is insufficient discussion on the issue of the premature termination of higher education

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Disadvantaged students at higher education institutions

The path of disadvantaged students towards higher education is not easy

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Conclusion

Education enables individuals to find their place in society. In addition to preparing them for the job market, it also guides them to take responsibility for their own actions. The decision to study at a higher education institution should be made freely, and motivated not just by gaining a degree as an entry ticket to the job market, but also by a desire to improve and grow. A higher education degree is currently a crucial requirement for better opportunities in the job market, but a degree alone is no longer sufficient. The employers of today have even higher expectations. They seek educated people

willing to work on themselves and capable of learning. Civil society also needs people who are responsible, motivated and engaged. Therefore it is important that higher education institutions do not only send the signal that they fulfil the role of qualifying people in society, but also that they are a space where everyone, without exception, can discover their qualities, grow as a person and develop their passion for learning.

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Transition from the undergraduate to the postgraduate level of higher education

[Available only in Slovak](#)

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Governance and management in education

Well managed schools create conditions for the high-quality performance of teachers, scientists and artists and thus, they contribute to a quality education for learners at all levels. Although findings from international surveys suggest that inadequate financing is a major problem, it is not the only reason for Slovakia lagging behind in this respect. From pre-primary to secondary schools, and also at universities, management staff do not receive professional skills training. Upon entering a management position in local schools, management staff are required to attend so-called leadership training. However, in the Learning Makes Sense survey, only a small proportion of school principals stated that such training had actually been useful for them in practice. At universities, management staff are prepared for management tasks mostly by performing tasks in more junior positions, with the positive effect of familiarising them with various levels of management. However, it can also contribute to management staff having only a narrow perspective of that particular university, and limited knowledge of other management styles and objectives. Moreover long-term employment at one particular school can lead to deeper ties among staff, and thus impede the adoption of unpopular, though necessary measures.

Management staff have a relatively wide range of powers at their disposal (ranging from personal to professional), but face many barriers in their actual application. One barrier is that, due to wide agenda at schools, management staff have no capacity to focus on the development of quality human resources and the teaching itself, as well as scientific and artistic activities at universities. This can negatively impact the school environment and overall quality of education. At private universities, it seems that owners tackle the economic and operational issues, while rectors and deans focus on academic issues. From the private universities participating in the analysis, all stakeholders perceived such a division of tasks positively.

At local schools, the division of responsibilities between school founders and school principals is unclear, and impedes the further development and regular operation of schools. At private and church-affiliated schools, the school founders usually actively seek information about their education content and outcomes. However, this is often not the case at public schools. In the case of many schools, their school founders perform only activities they are legally bound to perform, e.g. allocating funds, inspecting school financial management, or announcing the election of school principals. Many school founders let schools themselves manage their personal, economic and common operation agenda. However, many school principals lack support in these areas and it impairs their capacity to manage tasks related to teaching and professional issues.

At public universities, rectors and deans responsible for managing respective universities and faculties can only submit their proposals, while academic senates (coupled with management boards in the case of economic issues) approve them, which seems to be a problem. According to some deans and rectors, approval by academic senates makes their proposals more legitimate. However, at some universities, academic senates are places where the interests of particular institutes or faculties are advanced, instead of the overall interests of the universities. It seems that academic senates represent only a portion of students and employees. Combined with an absence of systemic data gathering on the performance of academic institutions, this state of affairs lowers the chances that a university can fully develop its potential. Students present in academic senates have a relatively high influence on issues with a long-term impact on their faculty of the university. However, at lower management levels (department, institute) there are no conditions for the systemic involvement of all students in issues related to the quality and conditions of their studies. Also, the rector as the top manager of a university has no direct influence on what is happening at faculties managed by deans accountable to the senates of their respective faculties. Data suggest that faculties and their additional elements (departments, institutes) tend to work independently of each other and even compete for students and resources. This negatively impacts on the quality of educational, research and artistic activities, as they lose their interdisciplinary nature and ability to solve current complex problems. Moreover, university managements are thus limited in their efforts to effectively manage their operational and administrative tasks. Apart from academic senates, scientific councils at university and faculty level

participate in university management. They should stimulate the quality of teaching along with scientific and artistic activities. However, data suggest that only some scientific councils have a majority of scientists with above-average performance at Slovak or international level, specifically in the case of social sciences and humanities. Since the study programmes offered and the scientific and artistic fields vary significantly, it seems that scientific councils tend to base their evaluation of career progress and study programmes on general and quantitative indicators. As a result, they are not always able to evaluate a particular programme or the work of an individual in accordance with the trends in that particular field. Lines of management at private and state universities are more simple. The Learning Makes Sense quantitative data suggest that students at private universities have more opportunities to shape the content and form of their studies, and their overall satisfaction with their studies is higher compared to their peers at public universities.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative data](#) from the Learning Makes Sense survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

School management in regional education

Management of local schools in Slovakia is relatively autonomous, but receives inadequate support

Management of universities

Management of universities is complicated and contributes to their internal fragmentation

Conclusions

An education system which is governed effectively thanks to a set of simple and comprehensible rules and professional management by people with leadership abilities creates conditions for high-quality performance from teachers and academic staff, and the holistic development of learners. The Learning Makes Sense survey findings indicate that quality school management at all education levels is hindered by complex and excessively detailed rules, and the wide scope of their agenda. Indeed, school managers are distracted from the strategic development of their schools and increasing the quality of their educational, scientific and artistic activities. Ineffective school management drains precious financial and personal resources at schools. An unexploited area for school development remains systemic data collection on school operation from various stakeholders' perspectives. It seems there are no procedures in place for the systemic involvement of students in improving the quality of their education. Since the school management system has various problems, it does not create conditions optimal for high-quality performance from teachers and academic staff, and for the education of learners. Not only the schools themselves bear the costs of this predicament, but society as a whole. Slovakia is thus missing out on high-quality scientific knowledge, people prepared for meaningful lives, and both the incentives and resources for economic, cultural and social development.

Author: Renáta Hall and Peter Drál'

School management in regional education

School management in regional education is relatively autonomous, but insufficiently supported

The most important actors in managing preschools, elementary and secondary schools in Slovakia are their principals and school authorities. The execution of their relatively broad competencies is made more complicated by opaque legislation and disputed responsibility for the various aspects of management. Neither the criteria for selecting candidates for school principals, nor the selection process are clearly stated. The most qualified applicant is therefore not guaranteed to become a principal. The principals are in charge of a very broad agenda, which distracts them from supervising the pedagogical process and developing human resources. School authorities could unburden principals from a part of their agenda, related to the operation of the schools. However, only a small part of them possess the necessary capacity, qualification and determination to do so. Thanks to the broad competence of the school principals, the authorities may not have a say in some of their decisions, despite sharing responsibility for the appointment and operation of the schools. School authorities are more often involved in approving the vision and strategic development at private or religious schools, compared to state or district ones. The execution of competence by school principals is further complicated by the fact that a part of the district schools is managed under the original tenets, with the other part under tenets transferred from state managed schools. This means that different schools and their individual organizational units are governed by different sets of rules and financed from different sources. Neither the school principals nor the authorities receive support sufficient for quality school management.

School districts do not have a direct impact on applicant selection for the role of principal. They only decide on the appointment of the selected candidate at the request of the school board. They are allowed to refuse a candidate, but they must justify their decision. If a candidate met the qualifying and other formal criteria, the justification of their refusal for a given position would be problematic. The authorities therefore tend to appoint the first candidate proposed by the school board. In lieu of qualitative criteria for assessing applicants in the selection process, and unclear procedural selection rules, the principal chosen might not be the most qualified applicant.

School principals have broad competencies, yet they are not fully autonomous in management, and face multiple obstacles in their decision making. The scale of the agenda they are in charge of, as well as the lack of administrative staff, limit their capacity to manage the educational process and human resources development. A quality pedagogical team, cooperation with the school authority, and a division of responsibility in school management have been identified as being of the greatest help by the school principals in the survey. However, when trying to build their teams, they continue to encounter labour and employment legislation that creates barriers to the firing of employees. At the same time, school principals do not possess sufficient resources to financially incentivise their employees and reward them for a good job.

The method of school management is closely related to the individual management and leadership skills of senior school employees. However, they do not receive the necessary methodological support to develop these skills. The compulsory functional education that they undergo in their positions is limited when it comes to encompassing all the varied educational needs in the area of management. A subset of the school principals expect practical advice on the school's daily operations from their functional education, while the more experienced principals expect a different added value that can be utilised in the strategic development of their schools. For this reason, only a relatively small number of school principals in the survey identified their functional education as something that had helped them in their roles.

Considering the scope of the agenda of management, the delegation of responsibilities to deputies, school committees and the teachers themselves appears to be an effective strategy for the principals.

School committees and the teachers play an important role, especially in areas directly related to the educational process, according to the principals. Participative management increases their engagement and motivation, and leads to a greater sense of identification with the direction of the school and a sense of shared responsibility for its quality operation.

Even though the principals in the survey identified collaboration with school authorities as being of significant help in managing their schools, there were certain areas in which a large portion of the principals could not rely on the authority. Many school authorities embrace only those functions sanctioned directly by the law; managing their budget and overseeing the finances of the schools. The authorities often do not have the necessary resources, capacity, qualifications or determination to unburden the principals from dealing with operational issues, personnel and their economic agenda, including public procurement. The school authorities also do not receive methodological support and aid appropriate to the practical execution of their capacities.

School boards and their district committees do not have a significant impact on the management of the school, according to the principals. This stems from the legislation stating that the only significant executive capacity of the school board is to carry out the school principal selection process and, based on its results, recommend a candidate for appointment to the school authority. Other than that, the school board is supposed to be involved in the conceptual direction of school development, but the decision itself is made by the principal. However, from the point of view of the principals, the impact of the school board on daily operations is relatively low.

School management at different levels of education, as well as individual organizational units of the schools, is made more complicated by the functioning of two management modes. District preschools, and organizational units at elementary and secondary schools, for instance cafeterias, extracurricular clubs and halls of residence, are managed and financed under the original tenets of the district. The elementary and secondary schools themselves however, are managed and financed under the tenets transferred from the state administration authority. These two modes are guided by different sets of rules and financed from different sources. This increases the administrative burden of schools and school authorities, given that the individual organizational units manage their own resources, file their own personnel agenda, process data independently, and answer to different authorities of state or district administration. The fragmentation of the operational and economic agenda therefore increases the time and personnel required for its fulfilment, and causes a waste of human resources. Along with the lack of administrative staff experienced by many schools, this can lead to the stretching of the senior staff, and rob them of their capacity for quality management of the educational process and school development.

The results of the [quantitative and qualitative data](#) analysis of the *Learning Makes Sense* project are presented in detail in the following sections:

The selection, competencies, development and execution of the role of the principal

School principals have wide competencies, but they encounter obstacles in their execution

[Available only in Slovak](#)

The execution of competencies by the school and district authorities

The school and district authorities aid schools only in certain aspects of management

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusion

The management system of regional education at the level of schools and school authorities is complicated. This is caused not only by the lack of transparency and extensive legislation, but also by the scope of the agenda and unclear competencies in various aspects of management. It complicates and prolongs the decision-making processes, and puts an administrative burden on schools and school authorities. The principals and authorities also lack adequate methodological support and education on strategic management, process management and human resources. As a result, it seems that many schools in the regional education sector are not managed efficiently, and are not always led by principals with strong leadership and management skills. When it comes to providing quality educational services, regular assessment and innovation, there is currently a lack of conditions conducive to teachers doing their job well, in such a way that would enable the holistic development of all learners.

Author: Peter Drál'

Management of higher education institutions

Management of universities is complicated and contributes to their internal fragmentation

The Learning Makes Sense data suggest that complicated lines of management at public universities seem to cause problems in their management. Proposals for the appointment and dismissal of a rector are submitted by the university senate, to which the rector has primary accountability. The faculty senate elects and removes a dean, and the dean has primary accountability to the senate. Therefore, there is no direct line between the university manager (rector) and managers of university entities (deans). Moreover, performance parameters linked to salaries are set by a different body from that which university managers are accountable to. This body is the management board in the case of rectors, and the rector in the case of deans. In the case of rectors, these performance parameters were known at several universities, but in the case of the deans surveyed, they were not. Insufficient clarity of assessment criteria applied to rectors and deans can pose a problem, because it is not clear what management results are expected from an organisation's manager.

Rectors and deans at public universities are at the top of their universities or faculties, but their proposals and personal nominations (including their closest associates, the vice rectors and vice deans) are often approved by academic senates, and in certain cases also by management boards and scientific councils. The academic senate takes decisions covering academic, economic, legal, personnel and institutional issues. However, according to the interview respondents, only some of the senate members have professional knowledge regarding university operation, and not all of them are high-quality academic staff. According to several deans and rectors, approval of decisions by the senate increases their legitimacy and improves original proposals. However, in crisis circumstances, such as the loss of accreditation or a financial source, this can increase the length of procedures. Senates, which contain members lobbying mostly for the interests of their own workplace, can impede proposals necessary for the institution as a whole but unpopular with some academic staff, such as merging workplaces with a similar focus, introducing interdisciplinary education, research and arts, or centralising and increasing the efficiency of administration and operation. Integrating universities further with their faculties is not supported by some senate members, nor by several deans and heads of departments/institutes, who prefer the autonomous management of their own units.

Only a part of academic society participates in the election to academic senates. Unlike students, who rarely participate, many employees take part in elections to academic senates. It seems also that employees with less work experience both vote and stand as candidates less frequently. At public universities, doctoral candidates are overrepresented among students in the senate, yet their problems resemble more those of academic staff than of students at the 1st and 2nd stage. This disproportionate composition of academic senates can pose a problem, because neither university administration nor senate members perform systemic collection of data related to the needs of all groups within the academic society.

The questionnaire survey findings indicate that the most frequent reason for the low participation of students in school governance is a lack of information about how to get involved and about the work of their representatives in senates. Also, some students are simply not interested in what is happening at their school. Low teacher participation in school governance was caused mainly by other duties they had, and also their fear of revenge by the school management in case they criticised something. This fear was strongest among academic staff with less than 15 years work experience, and full-time doctoral candidates. Also, respondents from both these groups perceived university to be a hierarchical organisation, unlike their student peers at private universities who were much less likely to have a fear of expressing criticism of school management.

Students have at least a third of votes in senates, thus they can influence many issues shaping their school many years ahead. However, survey findings indicate that students perceive these issues as being too abstract. Still, at the level of departments/institutes, where issues related to school subjects or teachers arise, there seems to be no systemic method of engaging students. According to the Act on Universities, students have a right to fill in questionnaires assessing the quality of their study and teachers at least once a year, but it does not seem to be an efficient tool.

Scientific/artistic councils at faculties and universities should stimulate the quality of their pedagogic, scientific and artistic activities. However, data suggest that only some scientific councils have a majority of scientists with above-average performance at international or Slovak level in the case of specific social sciences and humanities. Since the study programmes offered and scientific and artistic fields vary significantly, it seems that scientific councils tend to base their evaluation of career progress and study programmes on general and quantitative indicators. As a result, they are not always able to evaluate a particular programme or work of an individual in accordance with the trends in that particular field.

Academic senates at private and state universities are a more consultative body than at public universities, but this does not seem to be a problem for their members. The questionnaire survey even indicates that although students surveyed at private universities vote least frequently, they are much more satisfied with their studies. At private universities, students have opportunities to influence their studies outside the academic senate. At private universities, the lines of management are more straightforward. The owner of the university makes decisions about rectors and deans and is responsible for operational issues, thus freeing university managers to focus more on the academic development of their universities as compared to their peers at public universities.

Analysis of the [qualitative and quantitative data](#) from the Learning Makes Sense survey are examined in more detail in the following sections:

Selection of rectors and their powers

Rectors at public universities have a broad agenda, but the systemic regulations do not always provide adequate support

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Dean's agenda and position of their faculty within a university

Faculties, as basic elements of universities, have unexploited potential and resemble isolated islands

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Election to the employee section of academic senates

In academic self-government, the most active are the senior academic staff

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Nature of the employee section at academic senates

Current regulations for senates do not guarantee the professional experience of senate members, nor that their decision making will be to the benefit of the university as a whole

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Academic senates and their relation to university management

The relationship between university managements and senates is complicated by the Act on Universities and the internal rules at universities

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Students' representation in academic senates

A large proportion of students in academic senates does not guarantee relevant representation of student opinions

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Reasons for low student participation in university governance

Student participation in school governance is limited by lack of information, lack of time and fear of revenge from teachers and school management

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Nature of the scientific councils

Scientific councils have large powers and their tasks differ among various universities

[Available only in Slovak](#)

The quality of higher education institution research councils

Only a minority of higher education institutions' research councils is comparable to the international or Slovak average

[Available only in Slovak](#)

Conclusions

Public universities have a rather complex system of management. Despite this fact, there is no direct link between rector and faculties on the vertical line of management. This concerns both administrative and operational tasks. On the horizontal line of management, division between the drafting of proposals by the management and their adoption by academic senates poses a problem. Only some students and academic staff participate in senates. Lower participation in university governance by younger academic staff can slow down the development dynamics of their universities. The prevailing absence of students' voices in shaping their studies can point to the relatively weak role of universities in developing students as active citizens able to solve problems around them. Several questions remain concerning the scientific councils, and these might limit their ability to stimulate quality in education, research and art. Lines of management at private and state universities are more simple. It seems that students at private universities have more opportunities to shape their studies and are more satisfied with their schools. At public universities, which form a majority of universities in Slovakia, it appears management systems have several inefficiencies. These decrease their ability to create optimal conditions for studying and academic work. The relatively closed nature of individual parts of universities works against increasing quality in their education, research and art. It limits options for interdisciplinary activities that would be beneficial for the holistic education of students and exploring complex phenomena. The low degree of internal integration at several universities can

limit efficient use of personnel, material and financial resources in administrative and operational tasks at these universities. These resources could be used to improve supporting activities in education, research and art, as well as the universities as a whole. In other words, they are not disposed to improve the operation of universities.

Author: Renáta Hall

Methodology

The “Learning Makes Sense” project, implemented by MESA10 and in progress since 2016, is a response to the deteriorating quality of the education system in Slovakia. Its intention is to prepare a proposal for overall education reform from pre-primary to tertiary level. The objective is to change the education system in such a way as to reduce inequalities, address the needs and develop the potential of all learners as much as possible, and prepare learners to succeed in their personal, civic, and professional life. In order to prepare an evidence-based reform proposal, the project included an extensive analysis of the major problems in the Slovak education system, together with their causes.

Basic analytical framework of the data collection and analysis

The basic analytical framework was based on the education vision formulated in 2016. The vision describes what a quality education system in Slovakia should be like in 2040. The education reform proposal shall contain measures to achieve this vision.

The education vision was designed along three layers. The first layer involved mapping the strengths and weaknesses from pre-primary to higher education level which form the basis for planning the education reforms. The reform can build upon the strengths and develop them further, while the weaknesses must be addressed. Within the second layer, broader development trends in society with impacts on the education system were identified. These trends form a context that is independent from the education system, but has an impact upon it. The third layer consisted of formulating the envisaged state of the education system in Slovakia.

To define the three layers, an expert workshop was held in June 2016. The analytical team of the Learning Makes Sense project prepared the supporting documents covering strengths and weaknesses at each education level. Three working groups (pre-primary to general secondary education, vocational education, and higher education and science) discussed and reviewed these documents. At the same time, major problems in the Slovak education system were selected to be primary analyzed for the team. Each working group consisted of around 10 experts who have been dealing with these particular topics for a long period of time, either in the non-governmental sector, academic research, or in consultancies for international organisations (EC, OECD, WB, etc.). The output of the second layer was a map of broader trends in society as a whole. At the workshop, another working group focused on these issues with participating experts in the fields of demography, economic analysis, labour market, sociology, etc. The third layer drew upon a supporting document based on analyses of studies by international organisations, such as UNESCO, OECD, and the World Bank. The analytical output contained drafts of four possible scenarios for the education vision: education as a source of labour force; education as a human resources incubator; education as a global and local innovation hub; and education as a catalyst of social justice. International education experts discussed the four education vision scenarios at the workshop. At the same time, they were familiarised with the main findings about the strengths and weaknesses of the education system forming the starting point for the reform, as well as the broader development trends Slovakia is facing. Participants in this part of the workshop were international experts with experience in education reform in other countries (e.g. the Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Norway, Sweden, Hungary, the Balkans and the post-Soviet countries), along with participants working in non-governmental organisations, at higher education institutions and in international organisations (EC, CEDEFOP, OECD, the World Bank, etc.).

The education vision was formulated by the team in the Learning Makes Sense project based on the outputs from the specific parts of the workshop devoted to mapping broader trends in the whole of society, along with the strengths and weaknesses of the education system forming the starting point of the education reform. The education vision is the basic analytical framework for the analysis of the Slovak education system.

THE VISION OF EDUCATION IN 2040

Slovakia...

is an attractive, self-confident and innovative country, thanks to its new education system. It values every person and achieves prosperity by investing in human potential. It is a well-governed state that provides high-quality services addressing the needs of its citizens. Slovakia is actively interconnected with the world. It is distinguished by sustainable economic growth that ensures a high standard of living.

Education...

is highly valued in society. It contributes significantly to the happiness and satisfaction of people living in Slovakia. Education enables individuals to develop themselves, and it brings prosperity and coherence to society. It guides members of society to create fair and just rules, innovative and ethical solutions, and to assume responsibility for their own lives. Education respects and appreciates diversity; it is based on the needs and interests of learners, and motivates them to steadily improve thanks to customised support. Education is a quality and accessible public service.

The state...

guarantees equal access to quality education. From early childhood, all individuals have guaranteed access to a basic educational standard, and the state also supports various forms of further education. The state supervises the quality of education provision, collects and evaluates data and on this basis supports public discussion on the establishment and direction of education, science, and research.

The education system...

is governed effectively thanks to a set of simple and comprehensible rules, transparent decision-making, and the ethical behaviour of all stakeholders. The various education levels are open, flexible and allow transition between them. Following attainment of a basic educational standard, there is a wide spectrum of further educational choices available to all. This education system is based on the premise that learning is for life and can also actively shape the world around us.

The content of education...

is defined so as to enable the holistic development of learners. Besides the provision of essential knowledge and the development of relevant competences, it also cultivates learners' personalities. It supports healthy lifestyle, active citizenship, and ethical behaviour.

Learning environment...

is any place where purposeful learning and exploration take place across various disciplines, with emphasis on comprehension and placement in real-world context. The learning environment can take on different forms and enable learning in diverse ways. Teachers and other experts initiate cooperation with families in the best interests of their children so that they can attain the basic educational standard. Gradually, learners assume responsibility for the path of their education, career and life. The attainment of the basic educational standard enables learners to continue their studies, acquire qualifications and succeed in their professional career.

Learners...

are supported in their lifelong development and the learning environment strengthens their intrinsic motivation towards constant improvement. Learners have both the right and real opportunities to participate in decision-making about the content and form of their learning, taking their needs and interests into consideration. Learners are provided with a variety of help and support, thanks to which they actively seek out and grasp different opportunities.

Teachers...

are motivated, qualified and reputable professionals, able to recognise learners' talents. They master a wide variety of techniques and can choose the optimal learning method for every learner, in cooperation with other experts in this field. Teachers keep up with current scientific knowledge and involve learners of all ages in active exploration, experimenting with existing information and inventing new connections.

The vision provided a lens through which problems in the Slovak education system were explored at all levels.

The full text of the vision is available [here](#).

Goals of the analysis

The aim of the analysis was to find out what prevents us from realising the ideal state as defined in the education vision. Therefore the analysis aimed to analyse particular problems and their causes from pre-primary to higher education level, and to consider how they inhibit the education system from achieving the parameters defined in the education vision. Problems related to education policy as well as its implementation in various contexts were examined.

The problems and their causes were analysed in the following five areas:

Customised support for learners – diversity of learning needs that learners have; forms of educating learners with special educational needs; preparedness of schools to address the diversity of learning needs; accessibility and quality of external support; accessible and currently employed support mechanisms in education; customised education; career advice systems and opportunities for learners to participate in decision-making about their education path; financial support instruments in education.

Training and development of teachers and professional staff – attractiveness of the teaching profession; initial teacher training (selection of students for teaching programmes, education content and methods in initial teacher training, teaching internships for students), hiring and dismissing teachers; professional development of teachers (career system, further education, motivation and barriers to professional development).

Education content and methods – up-to-date content of education and its link to practice; interdisciplinarity in education; development of basic literacies, knowledge, critical thinking and thinking in context, creativity and entrepreneurship; holistic personality development, healthy life-style, and openness to new ideas; support for democratic values and active citizenship; teaching forms, methods and techniques; learning outcomes, assessment and verification).

Education openness, flexibility and permeability – flexibility and access to education for all; barriers to transition to higher levels of education, education options for disadvantaged groups – education tracks with a “dead end”; barriers to permeability between various education levels and

tracks; opportunities for life-long learning, demographic changes in the population of learners, outflow of students and academic staff to abroad, transition to labour market.

Governance and financing in education – major competences of actors in education and their exercise in practice; school network regulation and optimisation; school funding; competences as school founders for municipalities, church-affiliated and private subjects; school management; school facilities and infrastructure; collection, processing and use of data in the education system; evaluation and quality control in education.

The data collection had two phases:

Qualitative – in-depth individual and group interviews aimed to identify major problems in the Slovak education system, their causes and context in the respective five areas.

Quantitative – a questionnaire survey aimed to quantify findings from the qualitative data, i.e., to explore the extent and context (e.g. school types, regions) of problems in the Slovak education system that were identified during the in-depth individual and group interviews.

Qualitative part

Summary

The qualitative part aimed to identify major problems in the Slovak education system, and their causes and context in the respective five areas: customised support for all learners; training and development of teachers and professional staff; education content and methods; education openness and permeability; governance and financing in education, including quality assessment and development. The collection of qualitative data was implemented using the [methods of semi-structured individual and group interviews](#). In the qualitative data collection, [421 interviews \(398 individual and 23 group interviews\) were carried out in total](#), with 656 respondents from kindergartens, primary and secondary schools, including special needs schools, advisory and prevention centres, municipalities, private and church-affiliated school founders, state administration bodies in the education system – the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic (from here on MoE SR), district offices, organisations directly subordinated to the MoE SR (the State School Inspection, methodological and pedagogical centres), higher education institutions, the Accreditation Commission, representative bodies at higher education institutions, agencies for mobilities, grant agencies in science, non-governmental organisations, personal agencies and employers. Semi-structured individual and group interviews were administered based on [protocols prepared for each group of respondents](#) (e.g. school principals, teachers, students, other professionals, rectors, deans, HR managers and many others). Upon the respondent's consent, the interview was recorded, anonymised and transcribed verbatim. Most interviews were administered from [February 2017 to March 2018](#). Additional interviews aimed to explain several particular issues raised by the analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data were administered during July 2018–April 2019. Interview transcripts were [segmented and coded into main categories of problems](#) together with their causes and context that, under current education policy and its implementation, inhibit us from achieving the education vision in 2040. A method of thematic analysis combining both inductive and deductive approaches was applied. Basic categories reflecting the structure of interviews had been established before the analysis started, and they were later amended and refined. Triangulation of data sources served to interpret the qualitative data gathered, i.e. questions regarding the same issue were directed at several types of respondents (e.g. students, teachers, principals, school founders) and were also contrasted with data from other sources. The analysis was performed by the application Dedoose, which is a web-based tool intended for qualitative analysis, while enabling teamwork and the simultaneous work of several analysts with the same texts.

Quantitative survey

Summary

The main objective of the quantitative survey of the Slovak education system was to explore the extent and context (e.g. school type, region) of problems identified in [individual and group interviews](#). The quantitative survey was administered by [questionnaire](#). In total, 26 questionnaire versions were prepared for respondents from pre-primary up to higher education institutions, science, as well as from HR professionals. Questionnaires intended for various respondents contained common questions to gain an overview of a specific phenomenon from multiple perspectives. Questionnaires for students in the first and second cycle of higher education in Slovakia and abroad and for students at secondary schools were also available in Hungarian language.

The survey of respondents at pre-primary to secondary schools (except for students at secondary schools) was administered to a [representative sample of schools](#) according to the following survey quota variables: region, school founder, school type (only for secondary schools). Schools were selected by a stratified random selection method. [Selection of respondents](#) among secondary school students, higher education staff and professionals in HR was carried out by self-selection combined with intentional selection. Samples of secondary school students, teachers, scientists, and artists at higher education institutions, and higher education students in Slovakia (first stage, second stage, doctoral candidates) are representative according to prior selected survey quota variables. For two student samples (Slovak students studying at higher education institutions abroad, and academics and scientists working abroad) it was impossible to define the survey quota variables, because there is no information available about characteristics of these groups. Information gathered was interpreted only in relation to these respondents, as there is no exact information available about sample characteristics, and the same applies to [professionals in HR](#).

Questionnaires for respondents from pre-primary to secondary schools (except for students at secondary schools) and a part of the questionnaires for professionals in HR were administered in [paper form](#). Questionnaires for other respondents were administered [online](#). Multiple channels were used to communicate the call for participation in the survey and filling out the questionnaires. The questionnaire survey was administered [from](#) 26. October 2017 to 15. July 2018 (data from various groups of respondents were gathered later).

Processing the quantitative survey data for [pre-primary to secondary schools](#) and [higher](#) education institutions was performed by the statistical software SPSS. Based on the prior selected quota sample variables, data were re-weighted using the iterative weighting method (except for higher education students and academic staff abroad, as well as professionals in HR). The weighting aimed to simplify generalisation from the sample to the whole population. Various descriptive statistics were used for processing particular samples (minimum, maximum, average, median, modus values), and the Chi-Square Test and Z-Test were used for comparing column proportions. To verify dependencies between nominal characteristics of two variables, coefficients of association were applied: Phi coefficient and Cramer's V. To verify dependencies between nominal and cardinal variables, calculation of the Eta coefficient was applied. Data from the [professionals in HR](#) sample were processed by the statistical software Stata. Data analysis within the comparative analysis for particular industries, ownership types or enterprise size applied the Chi-Square Test and descriptive statistics. In total, 15,322 questionnaires were processed, from which 8,202 were completed by respondents from pre-primary to secondary schools, 6,902 by respondents from higher education and 2,018 by professionals in HR. The following tables present an overview of questionnaires processed for particular areas.

Table M_18 Number of questionnaires processed for pre-primary to secondary schools, by school type and respondent type

Number of questionnaires processed for pre-primary to secondary schools, by school type and respondent type								
School type	School principals	Teachers	Professional staff	Teachers in vocational education	Career advisers	Teacher assistants	Students	Total
Kindergartens	181	668	7	----	----	15	----	871
Special needs kindergartens	23	116	15	----	----	17	----	171
Primary schools	202	1396	106	----	145	214	----	2063
Special primary schools	83	650	29	----	67	29	----	858
Secondary schools	97	667	26	204	98	6	2823	3921
Special needs secondary schools	33	160	12	71	22	16	4	318
Total	619	3657	195	275	332	297	2827	8202

Table M_19 Number of questionnaires processed for higher education by respondent type

Number of questionnaires processed for higher education by respondent type				
School type/institution	Teachers, scientists and artists at HE education institutions	Higher education students at 1st and 2nd cycle	Doctoral candidates	Total
Higher education institutions in Slovakia	852	3835	614	5301
Higher education and research institutions abroad	197	1404	---	1601
Total	1049	5239	614	6902

Table M_20: Number of questionnaires processed for professionals in HR

Number of questionnaires processed for HR professionals	
Position	Number of questionnaires
HR specialist, recruiter, HR staff, HR manager	186
Other specialisation	32
Total	218

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